

Get out of Hair: Black Girls' Experiences of School Hair Grooming Policies in Jamaica

by

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Abstract

This research aims to shed light on the experiences of Black girls who wear natural hair in a predominantly Black high school in Jamaica. I employ a Black feminist methodology, utilizing conversations and observations to investigate how school hair grooming policies, under the directives of the Ministry of Education, impact Black girls' schooling experiences. Using an anti-colonial lens, I examine the stories of six female students at Sankofa High School (pseudonym) and the racialized and gendered logics embedded in the school's hair grooming regulations. I utilize Bacchi's "What's the Problem Represented to Be?" (WPR) approach to critically interrogate how Black hair is problematized within policy discourse and institutional practices. The research determined that although Sankofa High School's written policy does not prohibit any particular hairstyle, its enforcement reveals anti-Black sentiments on the part of teachers and administrators. Afrocentric hairstyles and those linked to anti-colonial resistance movements are often flagged as "inappropriate" for school, while straight hair is deemed "neat" and "well-groomed." Additionally, a texture-based hierarchy exists, in which kinkier hair types are more likely to be labelled "untidy" and in need of correction. The rationales used to judge hair reflect colonial logics that deemed Eurocentric features as the epitome of beauty and femininity, and Black hair as primitive and unfeminine. Although some students feel compelled to alter their hair texture through heat or chemicals, others actively resist them through everyday acts of defiance, critical questioning, and a desire to reconnect with their African identity. The study intervenes in the academic literature about race, beauty, aesthetics, and belonging in Jamaica and the wider Caribbean. Moreover, it contributes to public conversations about anti-Blackness in Jamaican institutions – which are predominantly led by Black people – and calls for educational policies that affirm and not regulate Black hair.

Preface

This thesis is an original work by Meshia Brown. The research project, of which this thesis is a part, received research ethics approval from the University of Alberta Research Ethics Board 1, Project Name “Natural Hairstyles in Schools,” No. 139384, March 4, 2024. No part of this thesis has been previously published.

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To my grandparents, Amanda and George Johnson. Your presence still lights my path.

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“Every mikkle mek a mukkule.” [Every little bit adds up to something bigger.] (Jamaican Proverb)

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Glossary of Hairdos

Hairdo/term	Description	Photo
<p>Afro</p>	<p>A hairstyle where tightly curled or spiralled hair is picked out from the scalp into a rounded shape (Sherrow, 2003).</p>	<p>Photo credit: CoverClap, 2024</p>
<p>Afro Puff</p>	<p>The hair is gathered together, like a ponytail, but with the ends left puffy/fluffy.</p>	<p>Photo credit: Healthy Afro Hair, 2019</p>
<p>Bantu Knots/ Chiney Bumps</p>	<p>Small coiled buns made by twisting sections of hair and wrapping them into mini-knots. The name “Chiney Bumps” is most commonly used in Jamaica.</p>	<p>Photo credit: Rochelle Ward, 2015</p>

<p>Box Braids</p>	<p>The hair is divided into square-shaped sections and braided - usually using three strands - into “boxes.”</p>	<p>Photo credit: Laifen, 2025</p>
<p>Cornrows/ Cancerows</p>	<p>Braids that lie flat against the scalp. The cornrows can be straight or made to form intricate patterns.</p>	<p>Photo credit: Braids By China, 2021</p>

<p>Dreadlocks/</p> <p>Dreads/</p> <p>Locs/</p> <p>Locks</p>	<p>Strands of hair that are matted or coiled together to form rope-like strands (Jackson, 2025).</p>	<p>Photo credit: Rony Kampalala Locs, 2023</p>
<p>Permed/</p> <p>Relaxed/</p> <p>Processed/</p> <p>Cream hair</p>	<p>These terms are used interchangeably to refer to hair that has been chemically straightened using relaxers or “cream” (as commonly called in Jamaica). The chemical breaks down the natural curls and coils to straighten the hair (Sherrow, 2023).</p>	<p>Photo credit: Hairlicious Inc., 2020</p>

<p>Plaits</p>	<p>Plaits are a braiding technique in which hair is sectioned, then that section is divided into three strands and woven together. While the word “plaits” is often used interchangeably with “braids,” the word “plaits” is used more frequently in this manuscript because, in Jamaica, plaits refer to individual braids that hang freely rather than being attached directly to the scalp (like cornrows).</p>	<p>Photo credit: Lynee, 2020</p>
<p>Protective Styles</p>	<p>Any hairstyle that minimizes manipulation and reduces hair breakage. These hairstyles include braids, twists, wigs, weaves, and locs.</p>	
<p>Slick Back</p>	<p>A hairstyle where the hair is combed or brushed back and held in place, typically with the use of gel, edge control, hair oil, or other styling products. The result is a smooth, shiny look where the hair is pulled away from the face and styled flat against the scalp.</p>	<p>Photo credit: Jen., 2016</p>

<p>Twists</p>	<p>A hairstyle where the hair is parted into sections, and two sections are wrapped around each other from root to tip.</p>	<p>Photo credit: Obiwulu et al., 2023</p>
<p>Twist Out/ Braid Out</p>	<p>The twists or braids are unravelled leaving a defined wavy or curly pattern.</p>	<p>Photo credit: Dokubo, 2017</p>
<p>Wash and Go/ Wash n Go</p>	<p>A style where hair is cleansed, conditioned, and styled to define natural curl or coil patterns.</p>	<p>Photo credit: Sherelle Naturelle, 2015</p>

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Why Hair Rules?

Fi mi granny always seh, “nuh matta weh yuh guh, rule deh deh — evn ef yuh guh a hell, yuh haffi falla di rule.” [My grandmother always reminded me that rules were everywhere — even in hell, you must follow the rules.] Her response came whenever I questioned the reasoning behind regulations that seemed arbitrary or unjust, like the school rule that insisted I could not leave my twists unbound. Why could students with straight hair wear their hair loose yet those with Afro-textured hair could not? The teachers at my school had similar responses to my questions regarding hair rules. The logic was simple: rules were meant to be followed, not questioned. But that did not sit well with me. I wanted more — more than just obedience, more than just accepting things as they were. I wanted to go beyond the surface — to get to the root of hair rules.

I am a Jamaican woman, born and raised. I attended high school in Jamaica during a time when natural hairstyles were not widely worn in the classroom. As a high school student, I wore my natural hair¹, but I was one of the few – in fact, I was one of the only three Afro-Jamaican girls with natural hair in a class of about twenty. My peers often asked me, “Yuh naah cream yuh hair?” [Why don’t you relax your hair?] which was their way of nudging me to chemically alter my hair. There were strict rules regarding hairstyle choice. I sometimes found myself in trouble for wearing zig-zag cornrows (see figure 1.1), twist-outs, and any form of Afro-puff hairstyle. Sometimes, teachers demanded that I go to the washroom to change my hairdo before I could be allowed to enter the classroom.

¹ Natural hair is used in this paper to describe hair that grows out of a Black person’s scalp in its organic state, unaltered by chemical straighteners, including relaxers and texturizers. Natural hairstyles include Afros, braids, twists, dreadlocks, and other styles that allow the natural texture of the hair to remain relatively unchanged.

When I became a high school teacher in Jamaica, I was confronted with the paradox of enforcing the very same rules I had once resisted as a student. At that time, I had opted to chemically alter my hair and wear hair extensions and other hairstyles. Many students also relaxed their hair, and those students rarely got in trouble for their hairdos. Black girls with natural hair, on the other hand, were often under scrutiny. It became even clearer that these policies targeted Black natural hair even though the majority of the population and the administrators were Black folks. The rules had been internalized so deeply that they were enforced and passed down through generations as if they were self-evident truths. But hair policies are not just about hair. They are tools to regulate the Black body, to force it into a mould that it was never meant to fit. This realization sparked some burning questions: What lies beneath hair grooming policies, and how do they impact the students subjected to them?

Figure 1.1

Photo Showing Three Variations of Zig-Zag Cornrow Hairstyle

Source. Ayub, 2024 - Tuko Media Ltd.

1.2 Purpose Statement and Research Questions

The purpose of this qualitative study is to understand how school hair policies impact female high school students in Jamaica. The research is guided by the following questions:

- How do high school female students experience school hair policies?
- How do female students perceive school hair grooming policies?
- What are the implications of these policies?

1.3 Background and Rationale

In his renowned statement, “Remove the kinks from the minds, not the hair,” Marcus Garvey, Jamaica’s first national hero and distinguished political activist, conveyed a resounding message. He urged Black people² to defy societal beauty standards by embracing the natural beauty of their kinky hair and their rich African heritage. There is no one single type of Black hair³ as it comes in a variety of shapes, colours, and growth patterns. Sherrow (2023) highlights the vast range of textures in Black natural hair, from thin to thick, and from nearly straight to gently wavy to tightly coiled curls. While most Black folks have naturally dark hair, some also have lighter shades, including brown, blonde, or red hues (Mercer, 2000; Sherrow, 2023). As noted by Oladele et al. (2024), scientists believe that the diversity in natural Black hair results from both genetic and environmental factors. One of the key functions of the dense, curly texture commonly seen in people of African descent is its ability to protect the scalp from the sun and facilitate the evaporation of sweat through better airflow (Byrd & Tharps, 2001; Sherrow, 2023).

Hair that is tightly coiled and spiralled is often called kinky hair. The word kinky emerged in the nineteenth century (Online Etymology Dictionary, 2025) and was originally used in a pejorative way to devalue Black hair (Henning et al., 2022). Sherrow (2023) notes that about 75 percent of Black folks have tightly coiled and spiralled hair that is described as kinky. If you run your fingers down a strand of kinky hair, you may feel bumps on the strand with sharp angles

² “Black” is used in this manuscript for people of African descent. The terms “Black people” and “people of African descent” are used interchangeably throughout this research.

³ Black hair is used in this paper to refer to the hair of Black people, not hair colour.

like the letter “Z” (Lilly, 2008). To remove the natural curls, coils, bumps, and kinks from Black hair, people often use hair straightening techniques like chemicals or heat to achieve a straighter look (Sherrow, 2023) (see Figure 1.2). Numerous sources, including Banks (2023), Byrd and Tharp (2014), and James-Gallaway et al. (2023), point to racism as the main reason Black people remove the kinks from their hair. Ever since the advent of Western colonization and the Transatlantic Slave Trade, Black folks have faced discrimination based on their natural hair. Sherrow (2023) notes that standards of appearance have historically valorized features associated with Northern European ancestry and “whiteness” — i.e., lighter skin tones and hair textures that are straighter, smoother, or loosely curled. Therefore, when Marcus Garvey implored Black people to remove the kinks from their minds instead of their hair, he wanted Black people to reject Eurocentric standards of appearance and rid their minds of colonial influences.

Figure 1.2

Photo Showing Kinky vs Straight Hair

Note. A girl shows her hair in its natural state on one side and straightened on the other.

Source. Brenda Mang, 2017 - YouTube

Almost a century after Garvey made this statement, Black natural hair remains a site of discrimination, as schools in Jamaica continue to enforce grooming policies that restrict Black natural hair and ban certain natural styles. Notably, in 2020, Jamaica’s high court ruled that a school had the legal right to ban a five-year-old child from entering the school because she wore the dreadlocks hairstyle (Elassar, 2020). According to *The Gleaner* (2020), the case began in 2018 after the five-year-old girl was barred from classes. The school had an unwritten policy of “no braids, no beads, no locs.” The primary (kindergarten) school she was enrolled in told her parents she would not be permitted to enter the school campus without cutting her hair (see Figure 1.3). The child’s parents insisted they would not cut her hair and took the matter to court.

Official court documents chronicle the arguments presented in the case of *Virgo v. Board of Management of Kensington Primary School*, where the 5-year-old girl, identified as ZV, was the complainant (see Supreme Court, 2020). Because the case involved the rights of a child, it fell under the responsibility of the Office of the Children’s Advocate (OCA), as outlined in section 14(1) of the Child Care and Protection Act. The OCA, represented by Shamsi Green, intervened on ZV’s behalf. Green challenged the school policy that prohibited students with dreadlocks from attending, arguing that it infringed on several of her rights under the Charter of Fundamental Rights and Freedoms, including freedom of expression, equality, humane treatment, respect for family life and privacy, and due process. Green asserted that keeping dreadlocks was not misconduct and that the powers given to the Ministry of Education to regulate school discipline should not extend to regulating personal religious expressions like dreadlocks. Furthermore, they argued that the policy was discriminatory, as it allowed other hairstyles but excluded braids, beads, and dreadlocks, thus violating ZV’s right to equitable and humane treatment.

In response, the school argued that the policy was not a law and, therefore, did not involve the right to equality before the law. It also contended that the attorney had failed to provide sufficient evidence that ZV was treated differently from other students with similar circumstances. The Court, led by Judge Sonia Bertram Linton, found that the policy was not a law, thus, not infringing on ZV's right to equality before the law. Regarding ZV's right to education, the Court concluded that the policy's hygiene-related aims were legitimate and that ZV's right to education had not been infringed, as she could attend another school that allowed dreadlocks. In the end, the Court upheld the school's policy, finding no violation of ZV's rights and denying the request to allow ZV to attend Kensington Primary School. According to *The Gleaner*, ZV's parents took the matter to the Court of Appeal, where, in 2024, the judge overturned the decision of the Supreme Court. The ruling states that ZV's constitutional rights to freedom of expression had been breached (The Court of Appeal, 2024).

Figure 1.3

Photo of ZV Wearing Locs

Note. ZV is a 5-year-old Jamaican student who was denied entry into school for wearing locs.

Source. Pryce, 2020 - *Caribbean Life*.

At the center of the *Virgo v. Board of Management of Kensington Primary School* case is the dreadlock hairstyle, also known as “locs” or “dreads.” Although dreadlocks have been worn for centuries in ancient civilizations such as Kemet (Egypt) and Abyssinia (Ethiopia), they are now most closely associated with Jamaican cultural identity, particularly through the rise of the Rastafari Movement in the 1930s (Sherrow, 2023). Bob Marley, one of Jamaica’s most iconic figures, wore dreadlocks as part of his Rastafari faith. Today, the hairstyle, along with other Rasta symbols, is widely used in souvenirs to represent Jamaica. Yet despite this cultural commodification and representation globally, students continue to be barred from schools for wearing dreadlocks. This contradiction on the part of the state raises serious questions about cultural acceptance, identity, and institutional authority.

The dreadlocks hairstyle is not the only one under scrutiny, as restrictions on Black natural hair and natural hairdos such as Afro and Bantu knots have also sparked public outcry. What is most concerning about these policies is that they often pressure Black girls to alter the natural texture of their hair. This disproportionately affects the majority of the student population in a country where 76.3 percent are of African descent and another 18.3% are mixed-race with African heritage (Jamaica | The University of the West Indies, 2025). A particularly noteworthy incident at a prominent high school demonstrates this point. The school’s principal faced criticism for banning Chiney bumps/Bantu knots – a natural hairstyle deeply rooted in the cultural heritage of the Zulu people of southern Africa. The principal described the hairstyle as “dramatic” and “elaborate,” yet permits students to wear straight hair extensions/artificial hair with a “natural appearance” (Korney, 2021). It is deeply troubling that straight artificial hair can appear natural on Black girls, even though straight hair is not typically a natural texture for Black folks, but natural hair is treated as a problem. This example sheds light on how contradictory

school hair grooming policies can be. They are often imposed on Black students by Black authorities in a discriminatory manner, hence the ongoing public debate about school hair policies.

Another notable incident that sparked public outrage and garnered the attention of the government occurred in 2017. A student was held down by three teachers and forcibly trimmed at a high school. As reported by *Loop Jamaica News* (2017), many people took to social media to question the logic behind the rules, with some folks stating that the “rules have outlived their relevance.” The public called on the Ministry of Education to create a national policy on hair and grooming to remove archaic rules and protect children from discrimination. Instead of heeding the cries of the citizens to create a national policy, the Education Ministry decided to create a “policy guideline,” which meant that schools would have the flexibility to create their own policies using the guidelines set out by the Ministry. The Education Minister shared his statement with *The Gleaner*:

“The ministry is going to give guidelines that you must go through a process that is legal and constitutional, and each school will have the flexibility to make the determination as to what the height of your hair should be etc... However, once it [the individual school rule] has been so established, it becomes the rule of the school, and the sanctions are to be also explicit. Indeed, you are to be very clear ... even providing graphical representation as to what the hairstyle is to be.” - *Ruel Reid, Minister of Education, Jamaica, 2017*

The Minister’s remarks suggest that the primary aim of the guideline is to ensure that school rules are legally sound. By setting the guidelines and allowing schools to make their own policy, the Ministry distances itself from the school rules and shifts the burden of accountability onto schools should legal disputes arise.

In August 2018, the Ministry of Education released its policy guideline titled “*Student Dress and Grooming: Guidance for Public Educational Institutions.*” The Ministry aimed to provide a framework for individual schools to develop their own grooming policies. As stated in

the document, the guideline was underpinned by five key principles: the rules must be rights-based and non-discriminatory; promote safety, health, and well-being; reflect moderation, reasonableness, and rationality; be practical and affordable; and foster positive values and attitudes. The document covered various aspects of dress and grooming, including uniforms, outerwear, accessories, and hair. However, while the Ministry intended for schools to create tailored policies for their own use, the guidelines fell short on specific directions regarding hair. The document acknowledged the complex, culturally sensitive, and emotive nature of Black natural hair and school hair grooming policies but refrained from providing explicit guidance on what hairstyles would be deemed discriminatory. In fact, the 48-page document does not mention any specific hairstyle that should be banned or permitted. Toward the end of the document, some sample rules are provided. These sample rules include:

- Hair shall be clean and neatly maintained
- Short hair evenly graded around the head, that is, using a guide comb or blade [specify number range], between [“x” mm to “x” mm]
- The following hairstyles are not permitted:
 - no fashion trends (as defined) including: [specify];
 - no shaved sides or patterns or lines;
 - no beads or similar accessories;
 - no hairstyles affiliated with known gangs or anti-social cliques or groups. (Ministry of Education, Youth & Information, 2018, p. 38-39)

While the Ministry of Education attempted to create a framework for schools, it failed to address the specific banning of natural hairstyles, such as Afros, locs, or Bantu knots. In the document, the Ministry acknowledges the historical legacy of colonialism, which created a “preference for lighter skin colour and straighter hair textures” (p. 13) but fails to provide any concrete guidance on how schools can prevent discrimination based on hair texture. Rather than outright condemning discriminatory practices, the Ministry takes a softer approach, merely encouraging schools to “overcome these challenges” (p. 13), leaving the issue inadequately addressed. This vagueness opens the door for inconsistent enforcement of hair grooming policies

across schools. It also absolves the Ministry of Education from being blamed, and protects the Ministry from legal repercussions.

Furthermore, the Ministry's stance that individual schools have the "final word in their application" (Serju, 2017, para.1) further undermines the document's effectiveness. The justification for this flexibility is that each school operates within its own unique context (Ministry of Education, Youth & Information, 2018, p. 2). This allows schools to make subjective decisions about hair grooming without being held to consistent or equitable standards. In essence, the Ministry's policy guideline is meant to "empower" schools to develop their own dress and grooming policies, but this approach has inadvertently maintained the status quo, permitting the continued exclusion of students based on their natural hair. This is evident as the ongoing issue of hair discrimination continues to surface in the media, with photos circulating of students standing at the gates of their schools or restyling their hair after being denied entry (see Figures 1.4 and 1.5). One parent, speaking to *The Gleaner*, asked a pertinent question: "Are we saying that your hair is a passport to access education?"

Figure 1.4

Photo from News Media

Note. A Jamaican student and school personnel assist another student with removing beads from the girl's hair before she can be allowed in class.

Source. Jamaicans OVA YAH SUH, 2022 - Facebook

Figure 1.5

Photo of Students Locked Out of School

Note. Students linger outside the school gate, barred from classes for inappropriate grooming.

Source. Hutchinson, 2023 - *Daily Observer* (Jamaica)

The need for a national policy on dress and grooming became increasingly evident after the *Virgo* and other incidents, leading the Ministry of Education to release another document in 2022 titled “*Student Dress & Grooming: Policy for Public Educational Institutions.*” The 2022 document was a draft, and in 2023, the final version was published. At first glance, it seemed like a step forward, as the title suggests the Ministry had finally created a formal policy rather than just a guideline to address the issue. However, upon comparing the 2018 policy guideline with the 2022/23 policy, it is clear that there are just a few changes made. A statement highlighting some of the controversial hairstyles was added. The new statement on hairstyles reads as follows:

A School Dress and Grooming Policy must provide guidelines that are concise and must not discriminate against students with disabilities and those with cultural differences. There must be no guideline specified within the Student Dress and Grooming Policy that promotes especially discrimination against natural hairstyles and it must expressly prohibit, regardless of gender or ethnicity, to include discrimination against African-centred, and other culturally specific hairstyles and headwear (e.g., afros, plaits, twists, locks, braids, cane row/cornrows, Bantu/Nubian knots, ponytails, hijabs, fades (school’s specifications for dimension contemplated) and any other hairstyle or headwear which is identified with a person’s ethnicity or cultural identity). (Ministry of Education and Youth, 2023, p. 22).

While it is commendable that the Ministry has publicly denounced discrimination against natural hairstyles, its position remains advisory, with no binding agreement. Schools retain the authority to create and enforce grooming policies at their discretion, hence, this research comes at a pivotal moment to investigate how school policies function in practice under the new directives given by the Ministry. This research draws on Nkimbeng et al.’s (2023) definition of hair discrimination as negative stereotypes and attitudes manifested consciously or unconsciously toward natural or textured hairstyles. Despite the prevalence of reports on hair

discrimination in Jamaica, there is a notable gap in research explicitly focused on Jamaican high school hair policies as mechanisms of hair discrimination. Prior studies (Barnett, 2016; Tate, 2013, 2017; Bourne et al., 2014) focus on hairstylization among adult women. Meanwhile, most of the scholarship on school-based grooming regulations is rooted in the U.S. context, where such policies have been critiqued for upholding the norms of the white-majority population. Jamaica presents a different case altogether: it is a majority Black nation where the very authors of these restrictive policies are themselves Black. This research, therefore, intervenes in urgent and important conversations around anti-Blackness, bodily discipline, and racialization within ‘postcolonial’ Black-majority nations. It seeks to contribute to the broader field of hair discrimination and adds another perspective to the discourse on race and structural power in Jamaica and the wider Caribbean.

Although boys are also impacted by hair grooming policies, this research centers on the experiences of girls. This is a personal choice, and not a claim that female experiences are more important than those of boys. However, as a Black woman, I approach this inquiry from a standpoint that is shaped by an investment in the lived experiences of females and the gendered dimensions of surveillance, regulation, and resistance.

1.4 Scope and Structure of the Thesis

What follows in this manuscript is an inquiry into Black natural hairstylization and grooming regulations. Chapter Two offers a review of the existing literature, situating Black hair within its historical, political, and epistemic contexts. I begin by examining the colonial roots of formal education in Jamaica, drawing on historical evidence to show how the current system is a direct inheritance from British imperial rule. Despite political independence in 1962, the

ideological foundations of schooling, its disciplinary logics, cultural hierarchies, and Eurocentric norms remain largely intact. From there, I trace the changing narratives of Black hair across key historical epochs. I start with the precolonial period where Black hair was a site of beauty, cultural identity, and spiritual meaning. Then, I will move through the brutal reordering of aesthetic value under slavery and colonialism, where African textures and styles were cast as barbaric and deviant. Following this, I describe the post-emancipation and post-independence periods, where the struggle over hair became a struggle over self-determination. Across each moment, I foreground Black resistance and show how Black hair is entangled in the logics of racial domination and the fight for liberation.

Chapter Three outlines the research design and methodological approach of the study. I situate this research project within a Black feminist methodological framework, which values the lived experiences of Black women and girls as sites of knowledge production. I explain the “What’s the Problem Represented to Be” (WPR) method that is used as a tool to analyze Sankofa High School’s hair grooming policy. Chapter Four presents the theoretical discourse that grounds the analysis. I explain how the anti-colonial discursive framework uplifts the voices of marginalized people and is used to interrogate the legacies of colonialism. I invoke the work of anticolonial scholars who interrogate colonial power structures and reject the idea that European ideals are the only valid way of being.

Chapters Five and Six offer a discussion of the findings. In Chapter Five, I use the WPR method to interrogate the hidden narratives and assumptions of the hair grooming policy that shapes the experiences of girls at Sankofa High School. I describe how the enforcement of the policy frames Afro-textured hair as problematic and in need of correction. I discuss students’ experiences of texturism and the negative impacts of the policy. Chapter Six focuses on Black

girls' attempts to value and care for their natural hair. I center the stories of students to show how a new generation of Black girls find joy in wearing their natural hair and using their agency to challenge colonial beauty ideals. I close this research with Chapter 7, summarizing the key contributions of research and suggestions for confronting the legacies of colonialism. I also present the limitations of the study and ideas for future research.

Chapter 2

Historical Context of Education and the Politics of Black Hair in Jamaica

2.1 Introduction

Hair is a natural feature of the human body, produced by physiological processes (Mercer, 2000). It is more than just a biological trait; as Mercer (2000) highlights, it is a cultural and social construct shaped by human practices. While hair is naturally a part of the body, it is rarely left untouched, as people often groom, style, cut, or conceal it, thus altering its natural state (Mercer, 2000; Tate, 2017). According to Sherrow (2023), the practice of grooming and styling hair predates recorded history. Hair grooming and stylization have moved from basic maintenance to becoming ways of expressing personal identity and making statements about one's place in society (Sherrow, 2023). In other words, hair is a medium through which cultural values, societal norms, and individual expression are communicated.

I begin this chapter by tracing the historical trajectories of education in Jamaica. I discuss how colonial rule, missionary schooling, and post-independence adaptations created the conditions for the racialized, gendered, and classed structures that persist in the present. I, then, change the course of the discussion to focus on Black hair and Black hairstylization. I start with the continent of Africa to understand Black hair grooming and stylization in pre-colonial African communities. Following this, the discussion shifts to the colonial period to examine changes in grooming practices and the narratives that became attached to Black hair due to Western colonization. I examine plantation life in the Caribbean and the ways that enslaved people navigated hair grooming under bondage.

The chapter then pivots to the post-emancipation era, where Black hair took on various meanings within cultural assimilation and resistance movements in the Americas. In the final

section, I look at contemporary issues surrounding hair grooming and hairstylization within the educational context. Drawing on recent research studies, I explore hair discrimination within hair grooming policies and their implications for Black girls. The purpose of this literature review is to trace the historical changes in the meanings and values attached to Black hair to gain a deep understanding of the origins of hair discrimination and the factors influencing school hair grooming policies.

2.2 The Colonial Foundations of Jamaican Schooling

Jamaica is a small island nation in the Caribbean, covering approximately 4,240 square miles (World Atlas, 2023). With an estimated population of 2.8 million people (The University of the West Indies, 2025), the island has a rich historical and cultural heritage. The original inhabitants of Jamaica were the Taíno people, who are believed to have settled on the island as early as 600 AD (Baldeosingh & Mahase, 2011). The Taíno named the island *Xaymaca*, which translates to “land of wood and water” (Jamaica Information Service, 2025). The term “Taíno” is derived from the word meaning “men of the good” or “noble” (Morgan, 2024). For centuries, the Taíno led quiet and peaceful lives, undisturbed by outsiders, until their lives were interrupted by Spanish voyagers (Jamaica Information Service, 2025).

Christopher Columbus arrived on the island in 1494, believing there was gold there (Morgan, 2024). He annexed the island in the name of the Spanish crown, despite the presence of the Taínos. The Spanish colonizers subjected the Taíno to extreme violence, enslavement, and European diseases, which decimated the Taíno population (Jamaica Information Service, 2025). In 1509, Juan de Esquivel was sent to establish a permanent Spanish colony, and Jamaica remained under Spanish rule until it was conquered by the British in 1655 (Morgan, 2024). The British colonization of Jamaica led to the expansion of plantations producing sugar, rum, and

molasses, with Africans enslaved and transported to Jamaica to provide labour on these plantations (Jamaica Information Service, 2025). The enslaved population received full emancipation in 1838, but Jamaica remained a British colony until it achieved political independence in 1962 (Jamaica Information Service, 2025).

Jamaica's formal education system has been shaped by its British colonial history. The education system established during the British colonial period was developed to serve the white elites (Miller & Monroe, 2014; Thomas-Brown, 2021). While the island's wealthy white settlers would send their children to boarding school in Britain, Miller & Monroe (2014) note that some planters believed the poor white boys needed to be educated to support the plantation system. Miller & Monroe (2014) explain that white planters bequeathed funds through their wills to establish schools to educate poor white boys. Notable institutions such as Wolmer's Boys School (1729), St. Jago (1744), and Titchfield (1786) were established through bequests and continue to operate today. As Miller and Monroe (2014) assert, these schools are regarded as the "nucleus of the so-called prestigious traditional high schools" to which families from all social strata now aspire to send their children (p. 222). In the late 18th century, according to Thomas-Brown (2021), the Anglican Church began to establish schools catering primarily to white boys. Over time, however, the admission policies gradually expanded to include Jewish and mixed-race boys, albeit under "certain conditions" (Miller & Monroe, 2014, p. 222). By the end of the 18th century, some schools began to admit white girls.

Miller & Monroe (2014) explain that education during slavery was primarily a tool to maintain the racial, gender, and class hierarchical structures, training different groups of people for specific roles in the plantation economy. As Thomas-Brown (2021) illustrates, girls predominantly received training in domestic skills, and boys were prepared for roles in

agriculture and estate management. After the emancipation of enslaved Africans in 1838, missionaries took the lead in developing elementary education for the freed population (Miller & Monroe, 2014; Thomas-Brown, 2021). According to Thomas-Brown (2021), these schools sought to integrate the former slaves into the colonial economy, often with a curriculum designed to create a compliant, lower-class workforce. By the 1860s, the colonial government assumed control over these missionary-run schools (Miller & Monroe, 2014; Thomas-Brown, 2021). This shift was largely in response to the Morant Bay Rebellion of 1865, an uprising in which the Black Jamaican population clashed with colonial authorities over poor living conditions and lack of political rights (Baldeosingh & Mahase, 2011). Thomas-Brown notes that not much had changed, as the government's educational policy emphasized basic literacy and numeracy to prepare the Black masses for low-skilled labour in agriculture.

Upon gaining independence in 1962, Jamaica inherited an education system that was shaped by British colonial practices (Bourne & Owen-Wright, 2018; Miller, 1999; Miller & Monroe, 2014; Thomas-Brown, 2021). While political sovereignty was achieved, the educational system continued to reflect colonial values and goals, including its focus on academic subjects that prepared the Black working-class population for low-level roles in the colonial economy (Bourne & Owen-Wright, 2018). According to Miller (1999), significant reforms to the Jamaican education system did not occur until the 1970s under the leadership of Prime Minister Michael Manley. In 1972, the government introduced the Free Education Plan (FEP), which sought to provide all Jamaican children with access to free education regardless of their socioeconomic background (Bourne & Owen-Wright, 2018; Miller, 1999; Miller & Monroe, 2014; Thomas-Brown, 2021). Despite these reforms, Owen-Wright (2015) contends that Jamaica's education system continues to bear the marks of its colonial past. The structures and curricula of

the system replicate the British educational model (Owen-Wright, 2015). Furthermore, as Morrison and Milner (1995) assert, educational reform in Jamaica involved modifying existing structures rather than creating a new structure that would better meet the needs of the masses. They argue that achieving meaningful reform requires addressing the enduring inequalities that remain deeply embedded within the system.

Today, Jamaica's education system is overseen by the Ministry of Education, Skills, Youth, and Information (MoESYI), with the guiding motto "Every child can learn; every child must learn" (Ministry of Education, Skills, Youth & Information, 2025). The Ministry is responsible for setting educational policies, monitoring school performances, and managing the overall development of education and education reform for all public educational institutions across the island (Ministry of Education, Skills, Youth & Information, 2025). The system is structured into four levels: early childhood, primary, secondary, and tertiary education.

According to the Jamaican Education Transformation Commission (2022), the education system is one of the largest institutions in the country, employing over 25,000 teachers who educate approximately 580,000 students across more than one thousand schools. Jamaica boasts one of the highest pre-primary enrollment rates globally, with 93.4 percent of children aged 3 to 5 enrolled in school (Jamaican Education Transformation Commission, 2022, p. 11). The United Nations (2010) reports a 98 percent attendance rate for Jamaican secondary schools. However, despite these positive indicators, the United Nations (2010) highlights that the country still faces challenges related to educational quality, resources, and achieving equity.

2.3 Historicizing Black Hair

2.3.1 Black Hair Glory: Hair in Pre-Colonial African Societies

The story of Black hair traces its roots to the cradle of civilization - Africa. According to Johnson and Bankhead (2013), hair has held profound spiritual, social, cultural, and aesthetic significance for African people throughout history, from the ancient Nile Valley civilizations to the rise of Western African empires. Characterized by tight coils and spring-like curls, Black hair has been artistically moulded and sculpted in various forms, giving rise to unique hairstyles that are inseparable from Black people's identity, culture, and history (Byrd & Tharps, 2014; Sherrow, 2023). Stone Age rock paintings and clay sculptures stand as testaments to the cultural importance of Black hair. Sherrow (2023) states that images of women with cornrowed hair dating as far back as ca. 3000 BCE were found in Africa's Sahara Desert (p. 127). There are Nigerian clay sculptures from 500 BCE depicting people from the Nok civilization adorned with various braided hairstyles (see Figures 2.1 and 2.2). These artifacts illustrate the diversity and richness of hairstyling traditions in African cultures.

Figure 2.1

Terracotta Artifact Shows Hairstyle

Note. Terracotta artifact from the Nok Civilization depicting a detailed hairstyle, dated between 500 BCE and 200 CE.

Source. *Think Africa*, 2018.

Figure 2.2

Nok Civilization Artifact Shows Hairstyle

Note. “The Nok civilisation was bordered by the region of modern-day Niger to the north, Markudi town to the south, Benin to the west, and Yola town in the East.”

Source. *Think Africa*, 2018.

For pre-colonial African societies, hair was not just a fashion statement; in fact, hair played a significant role in the language and communication systems of various African cultures. Byrd & Tharps (2014) explain that the Wolof, Mende, Mandingo, and Yoruba people utilized hairstyles as a means to convey messages. A hairstyle could indicate a person's family background, tribe, age, or marital status (Banks, 2021). The Ifari Apakan, a half-shaved head hairstyle, was worn by the Aresa household, particularly those already initiated in the art of medicine and herbs (Agwuele, 2016). Warriors among the Fulani, Wolof, Serer in Mauritania, and Mandinka in Mali wore cornrows in their youth and dreadlocks in old age (Johnson & Bankhead, 2013). As Byrd & Tharps (2014) note, a young Wolof girl during the Medieval

African period (12th/13th century) would partially shave her head to point out that she was not of marrying age. A Wolof warrior would wear a particular hairstyle to show that he was about to go to war, and a widow would leave her hair unattended to show that she was mourning (Byrd & Tharps, 2014). The diversity and significance of the hairstyles were handed down through the matriarchs of each generation, with mothers teaching their daughters to style their hair from a young age (Byrd & Tharps, 2014).

Hair was also said to have spiritual significance in many African societies. For tribes like the Yoruba, Wolof, and Cameroon, a person's spirit was believed to reside in their hair (Byrd & Tharps, 2014). The Yoruba people referred to humanity as "the species that grows hair mainly on the head" (Sieber & Herreman, 2000, p. 95). Respect for hair among the Yoruba community is evident from a young age. Agwuele (2016) explains a Yoruba traditional belief that states that children born with knotted hair are considered a blessing from god and are accorded much respect. These children, called Dada, were viewed as mysterious, gods, kings, and powerful spiritual beings (Agwuele, 2016). According to Byrd and Tharps (2014), Yoruba traditions say that because the hair is the closest to the heavens, communication from the gods was passed through the hair to get to the soul.

The hair was thought to be so powerful that even a single strand could be used to cast spells (Byrd and Tharps, 2014). To protect their healing portions from spells and to add potency to them, medicine men in Cameroon adorned their vessels with human hair (Byrd and Tharps, 2014). According to Sherrow (2023), hairdressers held considerable importance in African societies due to the spiritual significance of hair. Sieber and Herreman (2000) describe how hairdressing was typically carried out by trusted friends or family members. This is because if an enemy gets hold of one's hair, it could be used to create a charm that would harm the owner (p.

67). Byrd and Tharps (2014) note that for the Yoruba people, everyone was taught to braid hair, and hair-braiding sessions were a time of bonding and fellowship.

The comb played a key role in creating, decorating, and maintaining hairstyles in pre-colonial African societies. According to Byrd & Tharps (2014), skilled hairdressers relied on hand-carved wooden combs, specifically designed with long teeth and rounded tips to detangle hair without causing discomfort. Sherrow (2023) explains that combs made from ivory were popular among the Bavarians and Amaraeans - two groups of people who lived in predynastic Egypt. The Fitzwilliam Museum in England showcases a variety of Afro-combs dating back as far as 6000 years ago (see Figures 2.3 and 2.4). The combs flaunt exquisite carvings with geometric designs, and some with multi-coloured glass beads. The decorative motifs on comb handles often symbolized a person's status or cultural identity, featuring human figures, natural elements, and spiritual artwork (African Combs, 2025). Elaborate combs were often exchanged as gifts to commemorate significant life events, including puberty celebrations, weddings, and births (Tribal Art Muse, 2023). According to Byrd and Tharps (2014), before a skilled hairdresser passed away, she would give her box of hair tools to someone in her family who would take over her work. This handover took place during a special ceremony.

Figure 2.3

Ancient African Comb

Note. Afro-comb on display at the Fitzwilliam Museum in England.

Source. The Fitzwilliam Museum, Cambridge, 2025

Figure 2.4

Ashanti Wooden Comb

Note. Carved wooden comb from the Ashanti people of Ghana.

Source. Art Zimbabwe, 2025

Byrd & Tharps (2014) describe hair grooming in pre-colonial African societies as a meticulous process with various steps such as washing, combing, oiling, braiding, and twisting. According to Sherrow (2003), animal fats, plants, and minerals were used to style Black hair in ancient times. Palm oil, Sherrow (2023) notes, is known for its moisturizing properties and was commonly used to nourish and style hair. The hair was decorated with adornments such as beads, feathers, shells, flowers, wood, coins, or strips of material woven into the hair (Davidson, 2020; Sherrow, 2023). These accessories contributed to the overall hairstyles and sometimes signified a person's social rank, occupation, age and other traits. Furthermore, Chico (2013) observes that headwraps, crowns, and diadems were worn for daily and ceremonial uses. Ancient rock paintings dating back to ca. 10,000 to ca. 6,000 BCE depict archers and dancers wearing headpieces similar to those still worn in northern Ghana today (Chico, 2013, p. 8). In Egypt, “members of the royal family wore special head coverings, and the pharaoh wore a crown,

helmet, or a folded cloth kerchief” (Sherrow, 2014, p. 260). The Benin people usually covered their hair with head wraps only when it was not styled, but it was rare for someone to leave their hair unstyled. For many African tribes, Byrd & Tharps note, the hair was their “crowning glory,” and nothing was meant to hide it.

Hair grooming and stylization have long been integral to African cultural life and were sources of beauty and pride (DeLongoria, 2018; Johnson & Bankhead, 2013; Mercer, 2000; Sherrow, 2023). According to Johnson & Bankhead (2013), Black hairstyles have historically been complex and multifaceted, known for their artistic and symbolic qualities (see Figure 2.5). However, with the advent of Western colonization, these positive cultural associations and intricate practices surrounding Black hair were disrupted (Byrd & Tharps, 2014; Johnson & Bankhead, 2013; Ngandu-Kalenga Greensword, 2022).

Figure 2.5

Precolonial African Hairstyles

Note. Precolonial African hairstyles are replicated, showing a range of braids, twists, and sculpted patterns.

Source. folukeifejola, 2017

2.3.2 Colonial Oppression and Racial Resistance: Black Hair During Slavery

Sylvia Wynter, a prominent anti-colonial scholar hailing from Jamaica, centers the Columbian encounter of 1492 as being vital to the formulation of what is “normal” and what is deemed as the “other.” Through this encounter, a system of categorization emerged in the “New World,” wherein a version of humanness confined to the Western bourgeois archetype was constructed and imposed upon non-Europeans. This system disqualified Africans from humanness (Wynter, 2003), and race became a distinctive means of organizing a worldview necessary to justify the social, political, and economic order of colonialism (Césaire, 2023; Hall, 1980; McKittrick, 2015). The false notion that whiteness represented the standard of true beauty while condemning Black people to “eternal ugliness” was used to justify the racist construction of European superiority and African inferiority (Mercer, 1987, pp. 35-36). There is no evidence of Black hair being devalorized prior to colonization. As Johnson and Bankhead (2014) note, colonialism brought about a new phenomenon: “for the first time in history, African beauty, body and hair, was racialized, and European features became the accepted standard of beauty” (p.88).

The othering of Black bodies has been hegemonically forged and reinforced through dehumanization and violence (Banks, 2021; Johnson & Bankhead, 2014; Ngandu-Kalenga Greensword, 2022;). In his seminal work, *Capitalism and Slavery*, Eric Williams (1944) illustrates how the Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade was one of the most gruesome acts of violence recorded in history, implemented by the European colonists to feed their sadistic need for domination and economic exploitation. Byrd and Tharps (2014) point out that one of the first things the enslavers did to the African people was shave their heads (p. 10). While the colonizers claimed sanitary reasons for shaving the heads of enslaved people, scholars widely

agree that it was one of the initial steps taken to erase African identity (Banks, 2021; Johnson & Bankhead, 2014; Ngandu-Kalenga Greensword, 2022).

Stripped of their distinctive hairstyles, the enslaved Africans from diverse tribes found themselves deprived of a crucial means of identification while being trafficked to the “New World.” However, while in the Americas, enslaved Africans were allowed to grow their hair. This decision was rooted in the desire to preserve racial distinctions in the Americas. As Patterson (1982) argues, because skin colour could be blurred through miscegenation, hair texture emerged as a more reliable and visible marker of enslaved status. Patterson (1982) notes that differences between white people and Black people were more obvious in hair texture than in colour. Black hair, therefore, functioned as a “badge of status,” and leaving it unshorn served to reinforce the social and racial hierarchies that slavery depended on (Patterson, 1982, p. 135).

The violence enacted upon Black hair did not stop enslaved Africans from resisting colonial domination. Historical accounts highlight the ingenuity and resourcefulness of enslaved African women in utilizing their hair as a means of resistance and survival. According to Carney (2004), accounts from various communities in Suriname, Brazil, and South Carolina reveal that enslaved African women concealed rice grains in their children’s hair and brought them to the West. This led to mass rice cultivation in those regions where rice was not a plantation crop. This ingenious act of resistance symbolized not only defiance against colonialism but also ensured the survival and sustenance of future generations (Carney, 2004).

The oppression and repression of Black hair continued in the “New World” through various means. Scholars such as White and White (1995), Byrd & Tharps (2014), and Quampah et al. (2023) document the harsh grooming restrictions enslaved Africans faced during enslavement. Byrd & Tharps (2014) note that due to the long hours of toiling in the fields

combined with the inhumane and unhealthy conditions of slavery, many enslaved people were compelled to cover their hair with cotton kerchiefs. The enslaved also lacked the tools, particularly their precious combs, to care for their hair as they would have had in Africa. White and White (1995) elaborate on the limited grooming opportunities for the enslaved, noting that Sundays, their sole day off, provided the only chance to tend to their hair using whatever tool they could find (p. 69).

Due to the limited time for grooming hair and the absence of the traditional African combs, the enslaved people had to find new tools and techniques to groom and style their hair. As Byrd and Tharps (2014) noted, slaves resorted to using a “sheep fleece carding tool to untangle their hair” (p. 13). Furthermore, the enslaved Africans did not have access to the oils and herbal ointments they used in Africa, so they resorted to oil-based products like bacon grease and butter to condition and soften the hair (Byrd & Tharps, 2014, p. 17). According to Quampaha et al. (2023), cornrows became a preferred hairstyle, valued for their simplicity and ability to maintain a connection to African heritage. Cornrows were also used as a form of resistance. The hair was braided into intricate cornrow patterns to resemble maps, which aided in escape from slavery (Jordan & Oduro, 2023; Quampaha et al., 2023). Additionally, Quampaha et al. (2023) explain that the enslaved hid seeds within their braids to help them survive once they had escaped the plantation.

The enslaved Africans working within the confines of houses were forced to conceal their natural hair or adopt hairstyles that mimicked those of white colonizers in an effort not to offend them (Johnson & Bankhead, 2014). Scholars such as Bush (1981), Sanders (2011), and White & White (1995) posit that such regulations were propelled by the jealousy of white women, who aimed to establish dominance over Black women. White & White (1995) recount the story of

Sarah Rice's great-grandmother, who had "gorgeous hair which she had styled into ringlets, but her mistress didn't like it and took her and cut it all off" (p. 96). White & White (1995) also give other recorded narratives that illustrate the widespread practice of forcibly shaving the heads of Black girls and women who wore attractive hairstyles. Furthermore, hair chopping - oftentimes in an irregular manner - was a punishment inflicted by slave owners (White & White, 1995). Patterson (1982) also explains that the governors of some Caribbean countries issued orders requiring that enslaved individuals convicted of crimes have their hair cut off. Slave owners and mistresses used this as a "golden opportunity" to punish mixed-blood women with hair types similar to Europeans. Allain (2020) states that the punishment of hair-chopping was used on female prisoners in the British Caribbean, even in the post-emancipation era. While some people saw hair-chopping as a barbaric form of punishment, others believed that it was the only suitable means of disciplining unruly female inmates (Allain, 2020, p. 772).

2.3.3 Normalized Whiteness: From Slavery to the Post-Emancipation Era

One's closeness to whiteness functioned as a status marker during and after slavery (Davis, 2001; Ferrell, 1993; Hall, 1980; Mercer, 2000; Patterson, 1982). On the slave plantations, the enslaved people with lighter skin complexions and looser curls worked in the plantation houses doing less strenuous tasks than those working in the field (Baldeosingh & Mahase, 2011). According to Byrd & Tharps (2014), some light-skinned slaves with loose curls "tried to pass themselves off as free, hoping their European features would be enough to convince bounty hunters that they belonged to that privileged class" (p. 17). These practices align with Orlando Patterson's assertion in his book, *Slavery and Social Death*, where he contends that hair type was the "real symbolic badge of slavery" (Patterson 1982, p. 135).

White supremacist ideology was instilled in the psyche of Black people, and it continued even after plantation slavery ended (Ferrell, 2001). Black folks with light skin and straight hair, known as the ‘mulatto elite,’ tried to protect their social status by marrying other Black people with similar skin colour and hair texture (Byrd and Tharps 2014, p. 21). According to Byrd and Tharps (2014), some churches hung a fine-toothed comb from the front door, and if a person could not pass the comb smoothly through their hair, they were denied entry (p. 22). Science was also used to justify white supremacist ideologies and norms. As argued by Wynter (2003), scientific racism was employed to determine one’s level of humaneness, stating that Darwinism was crafted to justify the divide between the “naturally selected” (Europeans) and the “naturally dysselected” (those racialized as naturally inferior). White scientists pathologized and categorized Black hair, describing it as inferior and drawing parallels to animal hair (Thompson, 2009, p.833). German anthropologist Eugen Fischer used hair texture to determine the “whiteness” of people of mixed race (Dabiri, 2020).

After centuries of bondage and the enduring influence of colonial racist ideology, Eurocentric norms/whiteness became the standard of beauty. As noted by Byrd & Tharps (2014), by the end of the 19th century, the purpose of hair grooming had shifted from the elaborate and symbolic styles of Africa to a mimicry of white hairstyles. The desire to mimic white hairstyles and have straight hair was not just about upholding the standard of beauty, but, as Stuart Hall (1980) argues, straight hair carried economic and social advantages. One’s ranking on the “ethnic scale” determined one’s likelihood for social mobility (Stuart Hall, 1980). Additionally, straight hair signalled middle-class status and respectability (Byrd & Tharps, 2014; Davis, 2001), so many Black women straightened their hair “to gain access to jobs, education, and social acceptance” (Sherrow, 2023, p. 237). Black women found techniques such as stretching out their

curls with pieces of cloth, using oil and heat, or pressing hair with an iron or other objects that could be heated over a fire (Sherrow, 2023).

Hair care emerged as a significant avenue for economic advancement, particularly as the demand for products designed to modify or “tame” Black hair grew (Byrd & Tharps, 2014). Notably, Annie Minerva Turner Malone and Madam C.J. Walker were two of the most prominent “hair-care capitalists” of the era whose products were sold in the US, Latin America, and the Caribbean (Byrd & Tharps, 2014). According to the National Museum of African American History (n.d.), Malone patented a design for a hot comb used with oil to straighten hair (see Figure 2.6). Malone also developed a range of hair products aimed at making Black hair more “manageable” while simultaneously providing economic opportunities for other Black women through employment (Sherrow, 2023; Byrd & Tharps, 2014). Sherrow (2023) further highlights that Madam C.J. Walker, initially employed by Malone, launched her own hair care line and introduced her own version of the hot comb. According to Johnson & Bankhead (2014), Walker’s hot comb became more accessible to Black women who wanted to straighten their hair. Walker’s innovative approach transformed how Black women perceived their hair, and her enterprise grew into a million-dollar business (Randle, 2015). Critics argue that Malone and Walker’s products promoted Eurocentric beauty standards by altering Black hair to resemble a more “white” appearance (Byrd & Tharps, 2014).

Some Black people also experimented with chemical methods to straighten their hair, and hair straightening solutions were concocted in homes and in barbershops (Sherrow, 2023). According to Davis (2001), lye - a caustic alkaline component used for cleaning - was mixed with other ingredients found in the home to make chemical straighteners. In 1856, a Black man named Hodges demonstrated his lye-based hair straightener in New York (Sinclair, 1993, cited in

Davis, 2001). He left the straightening solution on the model's hair for too long, and the traumatic burning left their head bald (Davis, 2001). Subsequently, people added other ingredients to reduce burning. Sherrow (2023) notes that the “conk” hairstyle, which was popular among men in the 1920s-1960s, was made from lye-based products such as Kink No More and Kongolene Knocks Kinks. It was an expensive hairstyle with serious health risks, but those who could afford it were willing to take the risk, driven by societal pressures to have straight hair (Davis, 2001). The 1950s brought about relaxers that were less costly, reduced burning, and could keep the hair straight for a longer time, and by the 1970s, no-lye chemical relaxers were introduced, claiming to be more gentle on the scalp (Sherrow, 2023). However, scholars such as Davis (2001) and Farrell (1993) argue that damaged hair and scalps persisted among countless numbers of Black women suffering from burns and hair loss from the product.

Figure 2.6

Hot Combs

Note. Hot combs used to straighten curly or kinky hair, typically are heated on a stovetop or other heat source before use.

Source. Center for Black Literature & Culture, 2021

2.3.4 Victorian Ideals and Respectability Politics: Post-Emancipation Era

Throughout Queen Victoria's reign (1837-1901), Victorian ideals of beauty permeated global perceptions of femininity and aesthetics, shaping grooming practices in Jamaica under British colonial rule (Block, 2011; Buckridge, 2018). Sherrow (2023) explains that the Victorian ideals emphasized long, meticulously groomed hair as a symbol of femininity and virtue. Block (2011) describes the Victorian era as one fascinated by women's long hair with pinned-up hairstyles. Long hair was viewed as being ultra-feminine and desirable, but a respectable woman would not wear her hair loose in public. Loose hairstyles were frowned upon and associated with negative connotations such as seduction and amorality, prompting women to adhere to disciplined hairdos to maintain respectability (Block, 2011). The overarching principle was that women's hair should exude order and control, mirroring the societal expectations of women of that era.

Sherrow (2023) further illustrates the Victorian emphasis on cleanliness and the appearance of healthy hair reflected broader societal values. Sherrow (2023) notes that women, especially those from the upper and middle classes, were expected to dedicate significant effort to daily hair grooming routines to achieve the desired polished look. Block (2011) elaborates on the meticulous nature of Victorian hairstyling, where every tress was carefully pinned up to avoid any stray strands. Women would even avoid movements or activities that could loosen their hairdo. Harris (2015) explains that the use of fake hairpieces was common to enhance volume and create more elaborate hairstyles.

Victorian gender ideology permeated Jamaican society through various channels, including newspapers, which disseminated letters, articles, and reports of speeches reflecting Victorian norms (Brereton, 2013). Debates in publications like the *Daily Gleaner* newspaper in

1904, as highlighted by scholars Moore and Johnson (2000), underscored discussions on gender, respectability, fashion, hair grooming, and proper wifeness, reinforcing Victorian values. The influence of Victorian ideals extended beyond media representations into educational institutions, serving as another avenue for hegemonic imposition. Jeffery (1980) points out that schools in Jamaica, particularly before 1865, primarily catered to white families, and the school curriculum in the periods prior to 1865 served to transmit the ideology of the bourgeois class. This means that schools were intended to reinforce Victorian ideals, which included hair grooming standards.

According to Jamaican historian Steve Buckridge, many colonial subjects in Jamaica believed that adopting Victorian ideals of beauty and dress was a key way to improve their status. At the time, many people in Victorian England were able to use Victorian dress and grooming to acquire upward mobility. Many Jamaicans were also hoping that conformity would bring them the same (Buckridge, 2018). In the mid-1880s, as Buckridge notes, women from the Jamaican bourgeoisie, such as the governor's wife (see Figure 2.7), set the fashion trends, including clothing and hairstyles, which were then copied by other women in the upper and middle classes. Buckridge states that the new trend of mimicking Victorian hair and fashion allowed Jamaicans the opportunity to show that they, too, could embody elegance, beauty, and respectability within the colonial system.

For many Black Jamaicans in those days, upholding Victorian ideals was an arduous task. According to Buckridge (2018), while many colonial subjects saw conforming to Victorian standards of beauty, dress, and hair grooming practices as a pathway to social mobility, the cost of Victorian clothing and hairdos was often too high for most Afro-Jamaicans. He also explains that the dress and grooming norms of the Victorian era did not suit the active lifestyle of the

lower-class Jamaican population, who needed functional attire and hairdos for their daily activities. According to Buckridge, many Afro-Jamaicans adopted the Victorian styles, blending them with local traditions to reflect their unique aesthetic sensibilities. While they would wear functional clothes in their everyday life (see Figure 2.8), they wore their adaptation of Victorian styles – what became known as “Sunday Best” – to church or on special occasions. Buckridge also points out that many lower-class Jamaicans were not interested in imitating European clothing and hairstyles simply to climb the social ladder; some actively rejected the idea of adopting European norms as a form of anti-colonial resistance. “Afro-Jamaicans who did not observe these new standards were relegated by the normative taste of the period to the realm of the ‘uncivilized’” (Buckridge, 2018, p. 577).

Figure 2.7

Victorian Fashion in Jamaica

Note. Lady Musgrave, wife of Sir Anthony Musgrave, the Governor of Jamaica from 1877-1883. Known for her fashion trends and feminist work in Jamaica at the time. In the photo, she sports a pinned-up hairdo, fitting the Victorian standard of meticulously groomed hair.

Source. Thomas, 2020 - *Daily Observer*

Figure 2.8

Functional Attire in Victorian-Era Jamaica

Note. Photo from 1891. A Jamaican woman and girl wearing functional attire, dress and hair.

Source. MonoVisions Black & White Photography Magazine, 2017

2.3.5 Post-Emancipation Resistance

Despite strong pressures to conform to Eurocentric beauty ideals in the post-emancipation era, people of African descent have consistently resisted and challenged these norms. Political and social movements such as the Rastafari Movement, the Black Power Movement, and the Natural Hair Movement have played significant roles in uniting the African diaspora in the ongoing fight for Black liberation. These movements challenged Eurocentric beauty norms and fostered a sense of empowerment and cultural pride among Black people worldwide.

2.3.5.1 Rastafari Movement and the Dreadlocks Hairstyle

As outlined by Botchway (2018), “Rastafari started in Jamaica as an anticolonial Afrocentric spiritual and philosophical movement among the island's underprivileged people of

African descent in the 1930s” (p. 20). This movement was inspired by the teachings of Marcus Garvey, Jamaica’s first national hero and a Black nationalist who advocated for Black consciousness and pride during British colonial rule in Jamaica. Rastafari adheres to the teachings of Marcus Garvey, proclaiming that Black skin is not a mark of inferiority but a badge of honour and a “glorious symbol of national greatness” (Mthembu, 2011, p. 29). While colonialism relegates Black people to the sub-human category, Rastafari valorizes Blackness. Accordingly, Rastas sport their natural appearance with pride, rejecting the colonial beauty standard which celebrates straight hair, white skin, and careful grooming. For Rastas, Tate (2009) explains, “the straightening comb and chemical straighteners came to be seen as oppressive tools symbolizing the white-induced shame of natural Black hair internalized by Black women” (p. 37).

Edmonds (2012) further explains that Rastas denounced Eurocentric beauty norms by cultivating their so-called ‘nappy’ hair into knotted locks that came to symbolize Rastafari (p. 44). The dreadlock hairstyle, according to Sherrow (2023), dates back to various cultures, including Egypt and Ethiopia. Therefore, dreadlocks can be seen as a connection to African ancestral roots. In addition, some Rastas believe that having dreadlocks brings them closer to Jah (God), and as such, the cutting of the hair is generally considered to be Babylonian⁴ (colonial) conduct (Goldson, 2020, p. 375). It is interesting to note that the earliest followers of Rastafari did not sport dreadlocks, but rather, “it was a group known as Youth Black Faith in the early 1950s who popularized the matted hair complex” (Chevannes, 1995, p. 253). According to Chevannes, dreadlocks symbolized societal outcasts, lunatics, and derelicts in Jamaican society,

⁴ Rastafari uses the biblical city, Babylon, to refer to any oppressive societal systems, including Western colonialism, capitalism, and racism. This reference originates from the biblical story of the Israelites’ captivity in Babylon, where they were exiled and oppressed by a foreign power (as seen in Psalms 137:1-4). The last book of the Bible, Revelation, also describes an apocalyptic collapse of Babylon. Rastas find these stories fitting to describe their experience of being ‘exiled’ outside of Africa and their hope that their oppression will come to an end. (Edmonds, 2012).

and by embracing this hairstyle, Rastafarians physically manifested their rejection of, and disconnection from, Eurocentric societal norms.

2.3.5.2 Black Power Movements and the Afro Hairstyle

Figure 2.9

Women of the Black Panther Party with Afros

Note. Black Panthers from Sacramento at a rally in 1968.

Source. National Museum of African American History and Culture, n.d.

The Afro, originating from the term Afro-American, denotes a hairstyle characterized by thick, tightly curled or spiralled hair forming a large, rounded shape (Sherrow, 2023, p. 25). Because of the unique characteristics of Black natural hair, the Afro hairstyle, as Sherrow (2023) explains, is “well suited to the texture of Afro-Caribbean hair and is associated with Africans, African Americans, and Black Caribbeans as a natural way to wear their hair” (p. 25). Despite its name suggesting a link between Africa, Mercer (2000) notes that the Afro is not a distinctly African hairstyle but rather one that emerged in the African diaspora. As Sherrow (2023) explains, people of African descent, such as Frederick Douglass, wore their hair in an Afro before the 1900s, but it was relatively uncommon. It was not until the 1960s that the Afro gained

popularity and emerged as a cultural and political symbol during the Black Power movements in the United States (Byrd and Tharp, 2021; Mercer, 2000; Tate, 2009).

As written in the US National Archives (2021), “Black Power emerged as a revolutionary movement in the 1960s and 1970s, emphasizing racial pride, economic empowerment, and the establishment of political and cultural institutions.” Stemming from a response to ongoing racial discrimination, segregation, and systemic oppression faced by Black Americans, the movement aimed for the full liberation of Black people and expressed solidarity with anti-colonial and anti-imperial struggles in emerging Third World nations (Mercer, 2000, p. 39). The Black Panther Party, one of the most iconic organizations associated with the Black Power movement, adopted the Afro as part of its uniform. The Panthers were known for invoking the U.S. constitutional right to bear arms and urging Black Americans to arm themselves in self-defence against the murders, brutal beatings, and bombings of Black people by white racist police officers, the Ku Klux Klan, and others (Abron, 1986, p. 33). In addition to their militant stance, the Black Panther Party implemented community programs, including free breakfast programs for children, health clinics, and educational initiatives aimed at empowering and uplifting Black communities (The Dr Huey P. Newton Foundation, 2008).

Jamaica, among other Caribbean countries, experienced Black Power uprisings during the same period as the United States. Given that the Caribbean had a majority Black population, the Black Power Movement of the 1960s in the region emerged as a protest against local governments that were largely made up of Black officials (Quinn 2014). This meant that the nature of the movement in Jamaica differed from that of the United States. In Jamaica, people were fighting against a majority Black neocolonial state for its failure to deliver meaningful liberation to the Black majority in the post-Emancipation and Independence eras (Palmer 2014;

Rodney, 2019; Lewis, 2014). According to Lux (1972), Black Power also evoked a search for Jamaica's racial identity. While many privileged Jamaicans "exaggerated the degree of racial harmony" that existed and "promoted a form of Jamaican racial exceptionalism," the Black masses who often felt the brunt of racial oppression were not convinced of a unified Jamaica (Palmer, 2014, p. 113).

Radical advocates of the Caribbean Black Power Movement believed that the Black and brown middle class elites were complicit in upholding global white dominance by supporting capitalist and imperialist systems (Quinn, 2014). Black Power upheavals in Jamaica, therefore, stemmed from grassroots organizing and direct action among working-class and poor communities. While the Black Power Movement in Jamaica is often associated with the 1968 youth and student protests sparked by the government's banning of historian and activist Walter Rodney from re-entering the country, its ideological foundations are deeply rooted in local anti-colonial movements like Garveyism and Rastafari (Lewis, 2014; Quinn, 2014). As Palmer (2014) notes, the façade of racial harmony appealed to the Black and brown elites, but it was the Rastafari brand of Black consciousness that found deeper resonance among the Black masses. Activists demanded structural transformation, including land reform, educational decolonization, and Black political representation (Lewis, 2014). On the other hand, the government along with the Black and brown elites felt that the ideas of the Black Power Movement "threatened what they perceived to be a harmonious multiracial society (Lewis, 2014, p. 71). The Black Power Movement in Jamaica was met with state repression and elite anxiety.

Many activists in Jamaica were inspired by Black Power revolutionaries of the United States to wear the Afro. To them, the Afro represented more than just a fashion statement; it embodied a redefinition of Blackness and a celebration of Black pride. As Davis (1994) posits,

Afro radiated a sense of “revolutionary glamour” and the spirit of the movement (p. 39). While many Black communities across the globe embraced the ideals of the Black Power movement that the Afro embodied, others viewed it as reactionary, aggressive, and negative. Mercer (2000) provides compelling personal accounts illustrating this dichotomy, highlighting how churches condemned those wearing Afros, instilling fear and stigma around the hairstyle. According to Mercer, after a lifetime of believing that hair was meant to be straight, glossy, and neat, the Black church found the extremism of the Afro “unpalatable” (p. 62). This reaction encapsulates the societal norms and tensions surrounding natural Black hair and its anti-colonial stance during the era of the Black Power Movement.

The historical background on Black hair provides the foundational knowledge necessary for interrogating current educational hair grooming policies and practices. Understanding the cultural, social, and political significance of Black hair throughout history sheds light on the biases and coloniality embedded in modern grooming standards. Now, I will turn my attention to more recent research on school hair grooming policies. I will use a thematic approach to discuss the findings of recent empirical studies on hair discrimination in schools.

2.4 Previous Research on School Hair Grooming Policies

A review of previous research on hair discrimination in school grooming policies reveals three central themes: policy language and stigmatization, physical health impacts, and psychological effects. These themes offer important insights into how hair discrimination affects students’ experiences and overall well-being in educational settings. However, it is important to note that the studies discussed below are not based in Jamaica. They are findings from studies conducted in the United States and the United Kingdom. Despite an extensive search, I found no

recent peer-reviewed research specifically exploring the experiences of students with school hair grooming policies in Jamaican schools.

2.4.1 Policy Language: Stigmatization & Stereotypes

School hair grooming policies are often embedded in dress and grooming codes (Anderson, 2020; Banks, 2023; Gaddy, 2020). According to Gadson & Lewis (2022), schools apply stringent rules and harsher policies toward Black girls. Some scholars, including Gaddy (2020), Joseph-Salisbury & Connelly (2018), and Nkimbeng et al. (2023), contend that although these policies do not seem racially biased, they do, in fact, target hairstyles that are unique to Black students. This is shown in the language used in the written policy and its enforcement. Hair policies are found to be underpinned with negative stereotypes that label Black natural hairstyles as “unprofessional,” “unusual,” “unkempt,” “extreme,” or “distracting” (Anderson, 2020; Banks, 2023; Donahoo & Smith, 2022; Nkimbeng et al., 2023; O’Brien-Richardson, 2019; Shauri-Webb, 2020). They reveal that students sporting natural hairstyles are stigmatized as extreme, disruptive, unclean, unkempt, and undisciplined. The hairstyles they have identified as commonly vilified are locs/dreadlocks, Bantu knots, Afros, Mohawks, fades, cornrows, and twists.

Gadson & Lewis (2022) found that Black girls are expected to be “angry,” “ghetto,” and “promiscuous.” Gadson & Lewis (2022) explain that these imposed stereotypes and labels lead to Black students being overpoliced and underprotected in school. As O’Brien-Richardson (2019) notes, some students feel pressured to straighten their hair to reduce the likelihood of being negatively labelled. James-Gallaway et al. (2023) explain that Black hair in its natural state tends to be curly or coily and, therefore, does not conform to Eurocentric beauty standards that

valourize straight, silky tresses. Hair valuations harm Black females by promoting White beauty standards that devalue the hair textures and norms that are typical of Black women (Robinson, 2011, p. 358). Other research studies also show that the same negative labels used to justify the ban on certain hairstyles in schools are also found in many workplaces and even in the US military (Donahoo & Smith, 2022; Nkimbeng et al., 2023).

James-Gallaway et al. (2023) explain that students undergo “hair inspections” in school, and those who violate the grooming policies are subjected to punitive measures, including suspension, detention, expulsion, Saturday school, and prohibition from extra-curricular activities. Students, therefore, miss out on class time when their hairstyles do not conform to the standards set by the school. The literature also reveals that white students who violate the same hair policies often go unpunished (James-Gallaway et al., 2023; Lattimore, 2017; Shauri-Webb, 2020). For instance, when confronted with yearbook photos of white students with hair extensions and coloured hair, one school administration asserted that these alterations “weren’t as obvious” compared to those worn by Black students (Lattimore, 2017). Researchers argue that the over policing of Black students pushes students out of the classroom and can negatively impact their academic performance (Gadson & Lewis, 2022; Mbilishaka & Apugo, 2020).

The “communicated assumptions of aesthetics and a devaluation of Black girls’ hair” influence experiences of harassment and critique of their beauty and desirability (Gadson & Lewis, 2022, p. 18). Black girls report experiences of verbal harassment in schools. Norwood (2018) and O’Brien-Richardson (2019) document instances where Black students are teased, taunted, and ridiculed for wearing their hair in its natural state. Derogatory terms such as “nappy,” “hot mess,” and “bad hair” are employed by both male and female students, mirroring the discriminatory language embedded in school hair policies (Norwood, 2018;

O'Brien-Richardson, 2019). Beyond verbal assault, Black students also face physical harassment related to their hair. Mbilishaka & Apugo (2020) write about the unwanted hair touching by classmates and instances where Black girls' personal items, like hair accessories, are taken to provoke reactions and contribute to an environment of hostility.

Teachers, rather than acting as mitigators, often become perpetrators of hair harassment, upholding the colonial power relations. Mbilishaka & Apugo (2020) and O'Brien-Richardson (2019) report instances where teachers employ hair-shaming techniques, using racially derogatory terms to describe natural hair textures. This includes referring to a Black girl with short hair as a 'boy.' Such tactics not only undermine the self-esteem of Black students but also contribute to feelings of humiliation, embarrassment, and social anxiety (Nkimbeng et al., 2023). Despite the evident harm caused by hair harassment, O'Brien-Richardson (2019) found that school bullying policies typically overlook this form of mistreatment. The absence of explicit provisions against hair harassment within anti-bullying policies leaves Black students exposed to the risk of harm within the school environment. As Nkimbeng et al. (2023) note, the relentless harassment and pressure to conform to White hair norms causes some Black girls to feel excluded and negatively impacts their psychological well-being.

2.4.2 Psychological Impacts

Anderson (2020), Mbilishaka & Apugo (2020), and O'Brien-Richardson (2019) found that hair is a major source of trauma for Black girls who experience hair shaming, teacher teasing, exclusion, punishments, and other forms of discriminatory exchanges in school. The Association of Black Psychologists calls hair discrimination an "aesthetic trauma" and notes that the mental health effects of hair discrimination are dire, hence the need for the removal of discriminatory hair policies. Nkimbeng et al. (2023) contend that due to aesthetic trauma, Black

students are robbed of a sense of emotional security in school. They further explain that students who have had negative experiences with teachers enforcing discriminatory policies may develop a lack of trust in authority. Anderson (2020) and Mbilishaka & Apugo (2020) discuss the negative language associated with Black hair, the stereotypes, and the deeply distressing experiences which caused many Black girls to develop a hatred for school. Anderson (2020), Brown (2018), Mbilishaka & Apugo (2020), and Nkimbeng et al. (2023) found that aesthetic trauma is a lifelong encounter for Black people. Participants in the study conducted by Mbilishaka & Apugo (2020) describe how their painful nadir hair experiences began in school and continued into adulthood. The participants explained that they endure similar oppressive exchanges once they enter professional career settings, and there is an ongoing need to negotiate the appearance of their hair.

The need to constantly monitor and conform to these policies contributes to heightened stress levels among Black students in schools (O'Brien-Richardson, 2019). In addition, Mbilishaka (2018) points out that Black girls may develop improper coping mechanisms to navigate the psychological impacts, further heightening their risk of mental health problems. Moreover, discriminatory school policies contribute to the internalization of negative stereotypes and biases related to Black hair, causing low self-esteem (O'Brien-Richardson, 2019). These psychological impacts are long-lasting, and as Mbilishaka & Apugo (2020) note, Black parents are left with the task of undoing the effects of discriminatory policies by teaching their children coping strategies to navigate the psychological impacts of hair harassment. Black mothers in Mbilishaka & Apugo's (2020) study recall their children wanting to change their hair to feel accepted in school. They describe it as a "tug-a-war" - on the one hand, trying to maintain their

cultural identity, and on the other, trying to conform to societal pressures to adopt white aesthetics.

2.4.3 Physical Health Impacts

School hair grooming policies also influence the physical health of Black students. As shown by Mbilishaka & Apugo (2020) and O'Brien-Richardson (2019), the over policing of Black hair through school hair grooming policies forces Black students to alter the texture of their hair to avoid shame and punishment. Mbilishaka & Apugo (2020) state that these hair alteration practices involve chemicals and thermal devices. The use of chemicals and heat to straighten hair results in burns, physical pain, hair disorders, and elevated risks of other illnesses (Anderson, 2020; Donahoo & Smith, 2022). Respondents in O'Brien-Richardson's (2019) study reported headaches resulting from tight hairstyles intended to maintain a straight and neat appearance. Studies also reveal that the use of chemical relaxers in Black communities exposes individuals to endocrine-disrupting chemicals, some associated with adverse health outcomes, including breast cancer (James-Todd et al., 2021; Fillon, 2017). Black people are more likely to use hair products that lead to health risks, James-Todd et al. (2021) reveal. The half-trillion-dollar Black hair care industry reflects the substantial financial investment Black people make in styling products, surpassing spending by any other ethnic group (Donahoo & Smith, 2022; James-Todd et al., 2021).

Mbilishaka & Apugo (2020) and O'Brien-Richardson (2019) further explain that Black females are less likely to participate in physical activities when subjected to hair discrimination. They found that societal pressure to have straight hair that is "neat" and "tidy" makes it essentially impossible to maintain this ideal hair when exerting physical activity, which involves the disruption of straightened and styled hairdos. Gaston et al. (2020) maintain that wearing

natural hair reduces hair maintenance, encouraging Black females to engage in more physical activities and reducing cardiometabolic health disparities. Contrarily, schools, through their hair policies, create barriers to physical activities among Black girls, consequently elevating their risks of obesity, heart attack, stroke, and diabetes (Mbilishaka & Apugo, 2020; O'Brien-Richardson, 2019).

2.5 Conclusion

The history of education in Jamaica is inseparable from the logic of colonial rule. What the literature makes clear is that the system, as it stands today, modelled on British norms, was never designed to serve Black folks. Its origins lie in a project of governance that served to protect the interests of the whites and sustain the subjugation of Black people. Despite political sovereignty, the ideological foundations of schooling in Jamaica remain largely untouched, and schools continue to reproduce inequities grounded in the colonial past. The same ideological framework at the root of Jamaica's education system also governs perceptions of Black hair and appearance.

The literature demonstrates that before the advent of Western colonization, Black hair was deemed beautiful, and Black hairstyles served significant roles in African societies. There is no evidence of a ban or persecution of Black hair before colonization. The absence of negative labels before European contact illustrates the extent to which colonialism redefined Black aesthetics as ugly and of objects to be regulated. Nevertheless, Black folks have historically resisted colonial hegemony and oppression through their hairstyling practices. Unfortunately, Black hairstyles associated with anti-colonial resistance have been negatively labelled and condemned throughout history and continue in Jamaican schools today. The practice of associating Black natural hairstyles with negativity is a legacy of colonialism. As Mercer (1987)

aptly states, colonialism has “politicized our hair by burdening it with a range of negative social and psychological meanings” (p. 37). This highlights the cultural and political significance of hair, making it a necessary subject of academic inquiry.

While there is a growing body of research on hair discrimination in schools, there is a notable gap in studies explicitly focusing on the experiences of students in Jamaican high schools. Research conducted in schools outside of Jamaica show a concerning trend of policies that stigmatize natural hairstyles and the students who wear them, hair shaming by teachers and students, as well as physical and psychological impacts on Black girls. Given Jamaica’s colonial history and the cultural significance of hair within the African diaspora, it is essential to investigate how these dynamics manifest locally.

Chapter 3

Research Methods and Methodology

3.1 Research Design and Methodology

This study employed a qualitative research design to explore the experiences of Black girls who wear natural hairstyles at Sankofa High School in Jamaica (pseudonym). A qualitative approach was particularly suited to this research because it allowed for deeper insight into the topic, capturing the complexities of lived experiences that could not be easily quantified. As Tenny et al. (2017) highlight, qualitative research focuses on understanding the *hows* and *whys* rather than just the *whats* or *how many*, making it ideal for uncovering the diverse perspectives of Black girls as they navigate societal and institutional norms surrounding their natural hairstyles. Malik (2000) further describes qualitative research as a holistic approach that emphasizes understanding the perspectives and experiences of the participants in their natural settings. This allows the research to account for social, cultural, and institutional contexts that shape their experiences. By doing so, the research can “capture, inscribe, and re-present” the authentic voices of the participants (Denzin & Schratz, 1995, p. 313).

As a researcher who has intimate knowledge of the Jamaican school context as a student, and later in life as a teacher, positioning myself in relation to this work is vitally important because the methodological approach is deeply ingrained in my cultural framework. From childhood, I was immersed in the stories shared by my grandparents and community elders, whose narratives were laden with memories, hope, and life lessons. In school, we, Jamaican kids, were encouraged to read and share stories with others. Storytelling was not just a form of entertainment; it has always been a foundational component of our culture, and it is through the sharing of personal narratives that we make sense of the world, communicate what really

matters, and keep our traditions alive. This means that the Jamaican tradition of storytelling, which includes tales about Anansi the spider and Rolin Calf the mysterious bull, shaped my upbringing and was, thus, used to amplify the voices of this study's participants, who were girls in high school. Their stories are brought to the forefront of this research through a cultural lens that understands storytelling as a site of knowledge production, where Black girl voices are not extracted or translated as objects of research but valued and treated with an "ethic of care" and responsibility (Collins, 2022).

I married my cultural and historical ways of knowing with a Black Feminist Methodology, which is grounded in storytelling and is argued to be a liberating tool for conducting research (Collins, 1991; King, 1999). Patterson et al. (2016) describe Black Feminist Methodology as a way of constructing, analyzing, and interpreting narratives that center Black women and girls' experiences, voices, and perspectives. This methodology uses the lived realities of Black women and girls to produce scholarship that "uncovers, (re) defines, contextualizes, and validates" Black women's realities (Neville & Hamer, 2001, p. 437). Black Feminist Methodology not only validates local epistemologies but also challenges the dominant frameworks that have long devalued Black voices and ways of knowing (Collins, 1999).

Cynthia Dillard refers to Black Feminist Methodology as "Endarkened Epistemology" because it requires a break from Enlightenment philosophies (Dillard, 2000). Kynard & Pritchard (2022) explain that while Enlightenment thought, which emerged in the late 17th to 18th centuries, claimed to advance humanity through reason and progress, it also justified the atrocities of slavery and white settler colonialism. This historical contradiction is inseparable from the intellectual legacy of the Enlightenment, and it has shaped the philosophy of that era and underpins the Eurocentric research paradigms that still dominate Western scholarship today

(Collins, 1999; Dillard, 2000; Harding, 2023; Kynard & Pritchard, 2022). Research paradigms that are deeply entrenched in Eurocentric ways of knowing often marginalize or erase the experiences of Black women and girls (Collins, 1999; Crenshaw, 2023). As such, Black feminist research demands an intellectual shift — one that challenges these dominant frameworks and centers the lived experiences and knowledge of Black women and girls.

Sadly, “a large portion of research about Black girlhood utilizes a positivistic perspective, which focuses on variables that are ‘measurable’ and ‘observable’” (Lindsay-Dennis, 2015, p. 508). Such a research approach, rooted in Western epistemologies, fails to account for the richness of individual stories, emotional depth, and the interlocking systems of oppression that shape Black girls’ lived realities. These research methods reduce human experiences to mere data points while sidelining the voices of Black girls themselves. Black Feminist Methodology, on the other hand, centers the lived experiences of Black girls and ensures that they are co-constructors of knowledge in the research process. As Lindsay-Dennis (2015) states, “The guiding premise of this perspective is that ‘academic knowledge’ and ‘everyday experiences’ should guide researchers’ theorizing about [Black] girls” (p. 508), and Black girls should have “the right to interpret their reality and define their experiences” (Taylor, 1998). Patricia Hill-Collins (2022) reminds us that experience is a “criterion of meaning” and a fundamental epistemological tenet in Black thought (p. 258). Keisha-Khan Perry (2009) also asserts that experience is the lexicon of Black women’s lives and the source of inventing new forms of solidarity. Guided by these assertions, I allowed the students’ narratives to steer the inquiry and shape the data collection and interpretation processes. In addition, I actively engaged in critical self-reflection, as necessitated by Black Feminist Methodology, recognizing how my own positionality as a researcher informed and shaped the study (Evans-Winters, 2019; Lockett et al.,

2024; Patterson et al., 2016). By drawing on the Black Feminist approach to research, I aim to disrupt traditional research paradigms and amplify the voices of marginalized communities, allowing their perspectives to reshape how knowledge is produced and understood.

3.2 Research Site

For this study, I selected Sankofa High School (pseudonym), a site that aligned with both my academic and logistical needs as a graduate student. I first identified schools that had been publicly criticized on social media and in news outlets for their policies banning or restricting natural hairstyles, as these were directly related to my research topic. Regarding the logistics, I thought about my financial constraints and access to accommodation in Jamaica. I assessed the cost of travel, the availability of affordable accommodation, and the mode of commuting to the school. After narrowing down a list of potential sites, I began reaching out to school administrations to inquire about conducting research at their institution. The first school I reached out to was Sankofa High School, and I was pleased to find that they were willing to participate in the study. Sankofa High has faced public scrutiny over its hair grooming policies, hence, it seemed to be an ideal setting for this research on the experiences of Black girls with natural hairstyles. Additionally, the school was conveniently located near family members and friends, who graciously offered me a place to stay during my field work.

Sankofa High School is a co-educational secondary institution located in rural Jamaica. The school was established over a century before Jamaica gained political independence in 1962, and it has a reputation for producing top performers in the Caribbean Examinations Council (CXC) examinations, a series of standardized tests administered in high schools to assess the academic achievements of students across the Caribbean. The school has an enrollment of over

1,700 students across seven grade levels (Grades 7 to 13), ranging in age from 11 to 19. I focused on female students between the ages of 15 and 19 for two primary reasons. First, much of the outcry regarding the school's hair grooming policies has been centered on female students, as most of the banned hairstyles are typically worn by girls. This made it particularly relevant to center my research on their experiences. Second, I surmised that older students – those aged 15 to 19 – would have more extensive and nuanced perspectives to offer since they would have likely spent several years at the school. These students would possibly have more experience navigating the institutional policies and would have witnessed the changes in the school's hair grooming policy.

3.3 Sampling

To recruit participants for this study, I initially sought the assistance of the guidance counsellor at Sankofa High School. The guidance counsellor informed the upper-year students (grades 10 to 12) and the student leaders of the purpose of the study, and the students were allowed to ask me clarifying questions before deciding whether to participate. Participation was voluntary and open to female students with natural hair. Those who expressed interest in participating in the study were provided with an information sheet about the study and a parental consent form to be completed by their parents or guardians (see Appendix A).

A total of six students participated in the study. Two of the six participants are student leaders at Sankofa High School. The inclusion of student leaders was intentional, as they hold a unique position in the school and can bring a unique perspective. From my first-hand experience of being a student, student leader, and a teacher in Jamaica, I am aware that student leaders often serve as a bridge between the school administration and the student body, which allows them to

understand how school policies are perceived and enacted from both the administration's and students' viewpoints. Moreover, my experience as a student, student leader, and teacher has taught me that as advocates for their peers, student leaders are often privy to the stories and experiences of other students. Their role in ensuring that students follow school rules would provide a dual perspective that would be invaluable to this research and offer insight into both the enforcement and lived experiences of the policies. By including student leaders alongside other participants, this sampling strategy aimed to capture a broad spectrum of experiences and perspectives. For ethical reasons and to ensure the anonymity of participants, pseudonyms have been assigned to all individuals involved in this study.

3.4 Data Collection

In line with the principles of Black Feminist Methodology, which emphasizes the importance of context, relationality, and the centrality of Black women's lived experiences (Amoah, 1997; Clemons, 2019; Halle-Erby, 2024; Kynard & Pritchard, 2022; Lockett et al., 2024), I adopted an immersive approach during my time at Sankofa High School to better understand the experiences of Black girls wearing natural hairstyles. Rather than relying on formal interviews, I actively inserted myself into the students' everyday lives and school environments. I spent time with students in various spaces where they naturally gathered – music rooms, under trees, in libraries, at lunch, and during unassigned class sessions. From my understanding of the culture, I knew these were the spaces where students felt most comfortable and free from judgment, allowing for open, candid conversations. By entering these spaces, I was able to engage in authentic discussions with students about their experiences with natural hair, as well as their broader lives as Black girls. This is a way to challenge the Eurocentric notion of the

researcher as a detached observer. I saw myself as a learner-researcher in their lived reality, engaging with students on their terms.

While the students were fully aware of my goal to write my master's thesis on natural hairstyles in schools, I left it to them to bring up the topic whenever they felt comfortable. This approach was intentional, as I wanted to move away from the rigid, structured interviews commonly used in academic research. My goal was to foster organic and authentic conversations where the students felt at ease sharing their experiences with their hair. I ensured that the students led the conversations, shared their own stories, and revealed aspects of the topic that I had not initially considered. By being present in the students' day-to-day lives and even attending classes with them, I embraced the Black feminist understanding that knowledge production is inherently contextual and situated. Unlike the positivist approach, which tends to reduce social and cultural issues into isolated components, Black Feminist Methodology insists that these issues cannot be understood apart from the broader structural and systemic forces that shape them (Ladson-Billings, 2003). Black feminist storytelling allows Black girls to fully elaborate their stories, thus providing "culturally based perspectives that take into consideration the contextual and interactive effects of herstory culture, race, class, gender, and other forms of oppression" (Lindsay-Dennis, 2015, p. 506).

At the end of each school day, I reviewed my notes to identify points that required further clarification. These daily reflections allowed me to pinpoint aspects of the stories that needed deeper exploration, which I then followed up on through dialogue with each participant. These conversations were recorded to ensure accuracy, and they provided a space to deepen my understanding of their experiences wearing natural hairstyles in school, offering participants an opportunity to elaborate on the key themes that emerged during our earlier interactions.

Certainly, my prior knowledge of the Jamaican culture and subjective perspective on what points were most relevant inevitably shaped some of the questions and the direction of the follow-up conversations. This is antithetical to Eurocentric research paradigms that insist on maintaining an objective separation between the researcher and the researched, positioning the “power-bearing researcher” as a detached outsider and the participant as the “objectified” Other (Lindsay-Dennis, 2015, p. 507). In contrast, Black Feminist Methodology encourages a more engaged and passionate research process, where the researcher’s cultural lens and lived experiences are not sidelined in the name of objectivity or credibility (Lindsay-Dennis, 2015, p. 512). As a learner-researcher, my introspection, intuition, and passion are not separate from the research process – they are integral to how I engage with and interpret the lived experiences of the students sharing their stories.

3.5 Data Analysis

With parental consent, the conversations with the students were recorded to ensure accuracy in capturing the stories. The data was stored on an encrypted hard drive, and I used Otter AI transcription software to transcribe the audio. However, recognizing that the software does not reliably detect Jamaican Patois, I carefully reviewed the audio recordings and edited the transcriptions to ensure they reflected the true content and linguistic subtleties of the conversations. I read through the transcriptions and listened to the audio recordings several times to familiarize myself with the content, highlighting segments that stood out and making notes of recurring themes. I engaged in a process of open coding, where I broke down the stories into meaningful parts, attaching descriptive labels that captured the essence of the salient points.

Next, I employed a process of axial coding to connect these themes, looking for relationships between them and grouping them into broader categories.

Finally, I used selective coding to identify the central themes that unified the categories. Throughout the research process, I applied a lens of reflexivity, constantly considering how my positionality as a Jamaican woman with lived experience in the educational system influenced the analysis. According to Hesse-Biber (2013), “reflexivity is the process through which the researcher recognizes, examines, and understands how his or her own social background and assumptions can intervene in the research process” (p. 200). I kept a reflective journal to document my thoughts, biases, and insights during the analysis process to ensure that the participants’ voices remained central to the findings. I also utilized the WPR (What’s the Problem Represented to be?) approach to analyze the school’s policy document and the stories revealed by the participants. I will discuss the WPR method in the next section.

3.6 What’s the Problem Represented to be? - WPR Method

3.6.1 What is the WPR Method?

In this research, I apply the WPR methodology to analyze the Sankofa High School hair grooming policy document and the stories shared by the students participating in the study. The WPR (What’s the Problem Represented to be?) method is a critical approach to policy analysis developed by Professor Emerita Carol Bacchi from the Department of Politics & International Studies, University of Adelaide (Adelaide Graduate Research School, n.d). Bacchi (2009) contends that, unlike traditional policy analysis, which assumes that public policies are simply responses to external, pre-existing problems, the WPR method challenges this assumption.

Bacchi's framework focuses on how policies shape or "problematize" issues, revealing how problems are constructed (Bacchi, 2009; 2019a; Bletsas, 2012).

The WPR approach calls on us to fundamentally shift how we think about the relationship between policies and the problems they claim to 'solve' (Bacchi, 2009; Bletsas, 2012). Bacchi (1999) argues that rather than seeing problems as fixed and external to the policy process, policies themselves define and shape what is considered a problem. This shift in perspective opens up critical spaces for questioning the assumptions embedded within policy frameworks and examining the social, political, and ideological forces that influence policy decisions. I will give an overview of the theoretical foundations of the WPR approach before describing how the approach will be employed in its methodological form to discuss the findings of this research on school hair grooming policies.

3.6.2 The WPR Questions

Carol Bacchi first introduced the WPR method in her 1999 work, *Women, Policy and Politics: The Construction of Policy Problems*, where she sought to explore how policy interventions addressing women's inequality have been framed in Western societies. Bacchi (2009) explains that the WPR method was influenced by Michel Foucault's concepts of discourse and problematization. Drawing on the work of Foucault, Bacchi (1999) describes policy as a form of discourse grounded in the assumption that all actions, objects, and practices carry social meanings. These meanings, Bacchi (1999) argues, are shaped by the political and social struggles occurring within specific historical and cultural contexts. Therefore, policy must be seen as a cultural product, always "context-specific" (Goodwin, 2012, p. 29). Bacchi argues that policy discourses are practices that not only have real-world effects, such as shaping the identities and subjectivities of individuals, but also impose limits on what can be said, thought, or

done (Bacchi, 1999, p. 45). In developing a policy-as-discourse analysis, the WPR method reframes traditional policy study objects by moving from problems to problematizations, from identifying facts to questioning the nature of facts, and from assessing ‘what works’ to understanding ‘how things work’ (Goodwin, 2012; Shaw, 2010).

The concept of problematization at the heart of the WPR method refers to the way something is framed or represented as a problem (Bacchi, 2009, 2019a). To think problematically involves critically analyzing how a problem is represented and understanding the larger social and political forces at play, Bacchi (2019a) explains. Focusing on problematization helps us to identify the key influences that shape governance and how individuals are produced as particular types of subjects within those structures (Goodwin, 2012). The WPR method provides six critical questions I will use in my analysis to think problematically about school hair grooming policies. The aim is to unpack the assumptions behind problem definitions and explore the consequences of these representations.

The questions are as follows:

1. What is the problem represented to be in this policy?

This question asks policy analysts to identify how the problem is framed within the policy text itself. Bacchi says, “What we say we want to do about something, indicates what we think needs to change, hence what we think is problematic, hence what the problem is represented to be” (Bacchi, 2019b, 1:08). Although it may sound like a commonsense task, it challenges us to move away from the tendency to describe policymakers as ‘problem solvers’ (Bacchi, 2009, p. 3). Bletsas & Beasley (2012) posit that this question allows the researcher to recognize that the problem is not a neutral fact but a constructed representation.

2. **What presuppositions or assumptions underlie this representation of the problem?**

Bacchi (2019b) argues that every policy comes with embedded presuppositions and assumptions about causes, responsibilities, and potential solutions to the problem representation. Presuppositions, in this approach, refer to underlying background knowledge. What forms of knowledge do the arguments rely on to make them appear logical? What meanings must be in place for this logic to make sense? This requires looking for deep-seated cultural values (Bacchi, 2009, p. 5).

3. **How has the representation of the problem come about?**

The aim of this question is to “highlight the conditions that allow a particular problem representation to take shape and assure dominance” (Bacchi, 2009, p. 11). A probe into the roots of the problem representation provides insight into the power relations at play. It reveals where some groups have more power over others in ensuring that the problem representation sticks (Bacchi, 2009, 2019b)

4. **What is left unproblematic in the problem representation?**

This question urges us to critically examine the boundaries of the problem representation and consider the implications of its limitations. In answering it, Bacchi (2009) says we should reflect on what is excluded or overlooked, as these silences may reveal important perspectives or alternative viewpoints. We also need to scrutinize the elements of the problem that are accepted without question (Bacchi, 2019b)

5. **What effects are produced by this representation of the problem?**

Bacchi (2019) explains that this question asks us to consider the real-world impacts of how the problem is framed within the policy. It encourages us to think critically about the

consequences, both intended and unintended. In this regard, we examine how the framing of the problem shapes behaviours and societal attitudes. It reveals the power dynamics of who benefits from this representation and who may be negatively affected or excluded by it. Bacchi outlines three main types of effects: discursive, subjectification, and lived effects. Discursive effects refer to how discourses establish boundaries around what can be said, done, or considered relevant (Bacchi, 2019b, 51:22). Subjectification effects focus on how power shapes the subjective positions individuals are encouraged to adopt based on the way a problem is framed in policy (Bacchi, 2019b, 51:50). Lived effects relate to the material impacts of the problem representation on people's everyday lives (Bacchi, 2019b, 53:30)

6. **How and where has this representation of the “problem” been produced, disseminated and defended?**

This question prompts analysts to “consider the role of ‘actors,’ such as the media, as co-constitutors of problem representation - producing, disseminating, and defending them” (Bacchi, 2019b, 1:00:48). This analysis helps reveal how certain representations of problems gain dominance and become accepted as “truths” within society, and how they shape policy decisions and social responses (Bacchi, 2009, 2019b).

The WPR method provides a systematic approach to policy analysis, but in this study, I will use an integrated approach to discuss the findings. This means that while I address the WPR questions to examine the policy documents, I will also incorporate the stories shared by students about their experiences wearing natural hairstyles at Sankofa High School to illustrate key points. I will use an anti-colonial lens to think problematically about the problem representations and the overt or hidden assumptions embedded in the grooming policy. The anti-colonial

discursive framework (which will be explored in the next chapter) will deepen the analysis and critically uncover the broader social and historical contexts that shape the policy implementation. This integrated approach allows me to blend policy analysis with lived experiences to offer a robust understanding of the experiences of female students wearing natural hairstyles at Sankofa High School.

Chapter 4

Theoretical Framework: Anti-Colonial Discursive Framework

4.1 What is the Anti-Colonial Discursive Framework?

Dei and Asgharzadeh (2001) describe anti-colonialism as a discursive framework that allows for the “effective theorizing of issues emerging from colonial and colonized relations” (p. 300). Anticolonialism is seen as a discursive framework rather than a theory due to its flexibility in addressing the evolving complexities of colonial legacies. According to Shroff (1996), anti-colonialism provides “a guiding framework that takes into full account the fact that academic and political questions are continually changing to reflect social realities” (cited in Dei & Asgharzadeh, 2001, p. 299). Unlike rigid theories, which risk oversimplification, a discursive framework is adaptable, responsive to changing social contexts, and avoids the constraints of intellectual orthodoxies while interrogating colonial power relations and resistance (Dei & Asgharzadeh, 2001). Rooted in the fight against Western imperialism, anticolonial thought interrogates the nature of knowledge, culture, power, and domination which are built on colonial structures (Nunn & Whetnug, 2020). As Dei and Lordan (2016) explain, anti-colonialism is not merely a critique of colonial pasts but also a continuous process of challenging contemporary forms of colonialism and neocolonialism, emphasizing the importance of decolonization and the reclamation of Indigenous knowledge. In this sense, anti-colonialism is both a discourse and praxis (Bogues, 2011; Dei & Lordan, 2016; Hart, et al., 2017).

Simmons and Dei (2012) present twelve tenets as foundational principles for understanding and addressing the ongoing impacts of colonialism:

1. Anti-colonialism examines the dynamics of colonial and re-colonial relations and their impact on knowledge production, indigeneity, resistance, and subjective politics.
2. All knowledge must purposefully serve to challenge colonial imposition.
3. ‘Colonial’ is not simply ‘foreign or alien.’ It is ‘imposed and dominating.’
4. Colonialism never ended with the return of political sovereignty to colonized peoples or nation-states.
5. The anti-colonial framework theorizes the nature and scope of social domination and how power relations establish dominant-subordinate connections.
6. Engaging with the anti-colonial framework involves addressing concepts like colonialism, oppression, decolonization, power, agency, and resistance while affirming the authenticity and intellectual agency of local voices.
7. An integrated and intersectional analysis of colonialism, imperialism, and decolonization offers a deeper understanding of anti-colonialism.
8. Anti-colonial theory also emphasizes the importance of spirituality and spiritual knowledge.
9. The anti-colonial framework is grounded in the Indigenous sense of collective consciousness.
10. Anti-colonialism posits a literacy of resistance to bring about social change.
11. The notion of “white/colonial privilege” is crucial to anti-colonialism because it provides us with an avenue for asking and insisting upon accountability and addressing responsibilities.
12. It posits that the colonial encounter is transhistorical rather than historical.

(Simmons & Dei, 2012, pp. 73-76)

4.1.1 The “Colonial” in Anti-Colonial Discursive Framework

The term “colonial” is derived from “colony,” which Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2024) defines as “an area over which a foreign nation or state extends or maintains control.” Colonization, then, refers to the act of one group asserting dominance over the land, resources, languages, cultures, and relationships of another (Attas, 2024). This process is not a modern phenomenon; in fact, history is replete with examples of foreign powers imposing dominance over other nations. However, colonialism is not merely about direct territorial control; it is a far-reaching system of domination that encompasses the systematic subjugation and exploitation of local populations, their resources, and their knowledge systems (Dei & Lordan, 2016; Kohn & Reddy, 2006; Krishna, 2018; Sartre, 2001). Loomba (2002) notes that while colonialism took different forms in various regions, it always resulted in complex and traumatic interactions between indigenous peoples and colonizers. In this context, the anti-colonial perspective critically examines any situation involving imposition or dominance (Kempf, 2006). This is especially relevant in Jamaica, where European colonization and Western colonialism played a major role in shaping the nation's history.

The Spaniards were the first known Europeans to arrive in the Caribbean in 1492, and they found their way to Jamaica in 1494 (Baldeosingh & Mahase, 2011). Their encounter with the indigenous inhabitants of the Caribbean region marked the beginning of European colonization in the Americas. This meeting set the stage for a brutal colonial process that would dramatically reshape the global social order. Sylvia Wynter and many other anti-colonial scholars (Aimé Césaire, C.L.R. James, Frantz Fanon, and so forth) contend that the 1492 encounter marked “the invention of the modern/colonial Other” (Mignolo, 2015, p. 111). It played a crucial

role in the construction of race, identity, and power relations in the modern world. Wynter (1995) calls us to ponder:

“How... is the 1492 event to be perceived? Should it be seen from the celebrant perspective - as a “glorious achievement,” a “heroic and daring deed” of discovery and exploration, a triumph for the Christian West that was to liberate the indigenous peoples from their Stone Age, deprived existence without the wheel (Hart, 1991)? Or, is it to be seen from the dissident perspective - as one of “history’s monumental crimes,” a brutal invasion and conquest that led to a degree of genocidal extinction and of still ongoing ecological disaster unprecedented in human history?” (Wynter, 1995, p. 5-6).

Western colonialism brought about the creation of racial hierarchies that served to legitimize the exploitation, annihilation, and dehumanization of indigenous populations. The Europeans devised mechanisms that portrayed the European man as superior and their expropriation and dehumanization of indigenous people as not only a fact but a divine mandate. C.W. Mills (1997) explains that the creation of the *Requerimiento*, a document read to the Amerindians in a language they did not understand, which states that Christ entrusted the lands of the Americas to the Pope, is an example of how Europeans used falsely constructed religious and political narratives to legitimize dominion over non-Europeans. The native peoples of the Americas – whose ways of being and knowing differed from the Europeans – were deemed “not fully human” (Mills, C.W. 1997, p. 23). They were described as inferior, savage, and barbaric people who needed to be Christianized through European rule (Loven, 2010; McMahon, 2022; Mills, 1997, 2015). A similar narrative was used to justify the enslavement of African people. As Dei & Asgharzadeh (2001) point out, “Race, racism, and xenophobia lie at the heart of all colonialist and imperialist enterprises” (p. 309).

Quijano (2007) posits that the concept of race is arguably the most powerful tool for social domination. The racial hierarchy, which places whites at the top, Black people at the bottom, and other non-white groups in intermediate positions, became the core organizing principle of colonialism, shaping not only the Americas but also global power structures (Wynter, 1994; Quijano, 2007). These racial categories served to differentiate groups of people and legitimize the hierarchical roles of the colonized and the colonizer while denying the humanity of those classified as the “Human Other” (Dei & Asgharzadeh, 2001; Wynter, 2003). As Fanon (1961) points out, the ideological essence of colonialism is a “systematic negation and furious determination” to deny Black people of “all attributes of humanity” (p. 250). To this end, race was created as the criterion for deciding who belongs to humanity.

White supremacy stands as the flip side of racism, granting power and privileges to whites who have fabricated the fallacy of a racial hierarchy and positioned themselves at its apex. As Tlostanova & Mignolo (2012) explain, this idea of white supremacy and Black inferiority needed a system of knowledge to make it seem legitimate. “Once the idea was created, it legitimized the system of knowledge that created it,” and became a tool for dismissing other ways of knowing and being (Mignolo 1992, in Tlostanova & Mignolo, 2012, p. 42). Europe assumed the role of the authority on knowledge, presenting Eurocentric epistemologies as universal, scientific, accurate, and rational. Western science used Darwinian ideas to frame Europeans as biologically superior and Black people as inherently inferior, reinforcing racial hierarchies and relegating Black folks to what Fanon termed “Les damnés de la terre” [the damned of the earth] (Fanon, 1961). Angod (2006) aptly pens his interpretation of the colonial construction of Blackness, stating:

Blackness as it is conceived by colonialism and the history of the Western world, cannot co-exist with humanity. This is because goodness resides in the trappings of whiteness.

And blackness exists only to instantiate whiteness. By virtue of its degenerate characteristics, blackness gestures to the goodness of whiteness; it brings its opposite into being. Blackness, then, is a signifier for the ‘superiority’ of whiteness. (p. 162).

While the notion of race as a biogenetically determined concept has been thoroughly discredited, race continues to impact varied facets of life globally (Dei & Asgharzadeh, 2001). Indeed, as W.E.B. Du Bois in 1903 prophetically exclaimed, “the problem of the twentieth century [and even the twenty-first century] is the problem of the colour line” (Du Bois, 2022, p. 11). The Eurocentric perspective self-validates the colonial logic of biological value and dismisses any acknowledgment of the influence of power or other societal factors. However, Fanon (1952) reminds us that “besides phylogeny and ontogeny stands sociogeny” (p. 13). This means that an individual’s identity and experiences are not shaped solely by biological factors but also by the social and cultural environments in which they are embedded. Furthermore, colonial imposition not only legitimizes Eurocentric epistemologies but also demonizes and disregards other ways of being and knowing that are outside of the Eurocentric worldview. According to Hlabangane (2021), “these other ways of knowing and being are rendered unintelligible when filtered through Western sensibilities” (p. 166). To this end, Europeans see themselves as the most advanced of all species, and they propagate this perspective as hegemonic within the global model of power. Mignolo (2011) asserts that “the coloniality of knowledge and being have been created, perfected, transformed, expanded, imported and exported,” and therefore, dictate our ways of thinking and behaving (p.111). Through colonialism, the European way of life – i.e. the imperialist *whitesupremacistcapitalistpatriarchial* culture, as described by bell hooks (2014) – is positioned as the epitome of civilization.

4.1.2 The “Anti” in Anti-Colonial

The “anti” in anti-colonialism denotes the resistance against colonial systems of domination, subjugation and intellectual control. Anti-colonial thought recognizes that colonialism is not a singular event in history but a continuous process of power dynamics that must be critiqued and actively resisted in both academic and activist spaces (Lewis, 2012). Scholars such as George Dei (2006) and Sujata Patel (2023) emphasize that contemporary anti-colonial thought did not begin in academia; instead, it has its roots in anti-colonial and decolonial movements that fought for political independence from European powers, particularly in the aftermath of World War II. This theory, as Simmons and Dei (2012) note, “emerges from the ‘ground up’” (p. 76).

According to Dei (2010), most of the scholars – like Frantz Fanon, Albert Memmi, Aimé Césaire, Angela Davis, Marcus Garvey, and Kwame Nkrumah – who were instrumental in shaping anti-colonial thought were nationalists who were committed to resisting the colonial social order and promoting social change. When we read their work, we see references to anti-colonial resistance movements such as the Haitian Revolution (which resulted in Haiti becoming the first independent country in the Caribbean and the first Black republic in the world), Negritude (which sought to reclaim and assert the dignity and value of Black identity in France), the Civil Rights Movements (which led to the abolition of legalized racial segregation in the United States), and Garveyism (which aimed to achieve Black self-determination, collective unity, and economic independence globally). Anti-colonial scholars and activists saw the colonial order as a pervasive structure that demanded radical resistance and transformation at all levels of society – politically, culturally, and intellectually (Dei, 2010). As such, Dei &

Asgharzadeh (2001) assert that the strength of the anti-colonial framework lies in its ability to inspire social and political action.

Albert Memmi (1965), in his seminal work *The Colonizer and the Colonized*, explores the psychological and social dynamics of colonialism. Memmi focuses on the reciprocal relationship between the colonizer and the colonized. He argues that colonialism is a system of mutual dependency, where both parties are shaped by the colonial power structure. The colonizer's identity is constructed through domination, while the colonized are defined by subjugation. It produces a symbiotic relationship of "hate and desire." Memmi exclaims, "How could he [the colonized] hate the colonizers and yet admire them so passionately?" (Memmi, 1965, p. 6). Similarly, Frantz Fanon explores how Black people internalize the values and perceptions of the colonial oppressor, leading to feelings of inferiority, alienation, and mental enslavement. Fanon writes that "The Negro is the one who is always being looked at, and who feels himself 'looked at' by others... His inferiority complex is the result of a historical fact, a fact that is imposed by a world of 'whiteness' that exists and that reflects itself on him." (Fanon, 1952, p. 110). For this reason, anti-colonial theorization must also focus on the psychological aspect of colonialism. The "anti" in this context is then a rejection of the colonizer's constructed authority and the refusal to accept the colonizer's imposed identities. It is an unveiling and dismantling of the mental chains of colonial oppression.

Simmons and Dei (2012) aptly describe anti-colonial thought as an "epistemology of the oppressed" (p. 76). It directly challenges the dominance of Western knowledge by reclaiming and celebrating indigenous ways of knowing. Akena (2012) describes Indigenous knowledge as "a complex accumulation of local context-relevant knowledge that embraces the essence of ancestral knowing as well as the legacies of diverse histories and cultures" (p. 601). This

perspective aligns with Wane's (2006) assertion that the processes of colonization involved rewriting history to deny the colonizer's existence, devaluing their knowledge, and debasing their cultural beliefs and practices. Scholars like Dei (2008), Wane (2006), and Akena (2012) argue that the Western education system plays a crucial role in perpetuating a colonizing knowledge structure which systematically erases Indigenous epistemologies while reinforcing societal inequities based on race, culture, language, gender, and class.

For Indigenous communities, reclaiming their own knowledge systems is an essential act of resistance – one that challenges the narrative imposed by colonial systems and seeks to revitalize the context-relevant ways of knowing that were deliberately suppressed, branded as inferior, and dismissed as backward (Akena, 2012; Wane, 2006). Akena (2012) further emphasizes that if we do not develop counter-narratives that clearly expose and challenge systems of domination and privilege, Indigenous worldviews risk being lost. Therefore, anti-colonial theorists should aim to engage with oppositional frameworks and counter-discourses that draw on Indigenous concepts, analytical methods, and cultural perspectives (Dei & Asgharzadeh, 2001, p. 301).

Anti-colonial scholars contend that language plays a central role in the construction and imposition of colonial knowledge. Scholars such as Fanon (1952) and Mignolo (1992) posit that when the colonizers imposed their languages on the colonized, they simultaneously imposed their worldviews. As Fanon (1952) writes, "To speak a language is to take on a world, a culture" (p. 38). By forcing the colonized to adopt the language of their oppressors, colonial powers sought to dismantle indigenous worldviews, thereby erasing the very foundation of indigenous culture and identity. Mulder (2015) points out that, after the abolition of slavery, most of the former enslaved no longer knew the languages of their ancestors. This epistemic violence often

carries deeper psychological effects, reinforcing the notion that the colonizer's language – and by extension, their knowledge – is superior. Fanon (1952) illustrates how the Antilles Negro hones his French language skills as a way to prove his worth within the dominant culture. This is similar to Wane's (2006) assertion that adopting another person's language can be seen as one of the highest forms of colonization. Meighan (2023) points out that English carries with it a history of colonialism and imperialism that reinforces Eurocentric worldviews and upholds colonial power structures. Contrary to colonial hegemonic imposition, anti-colonial thought advocates for a return to indigenous languages as a means of reclaiming agency and cultural identity. Dei (2008) emphasizes the importance of indigenous languages in preserving knowledge and cultural heritage, arguing that “speaking back” through indigenous languages is a powerful tool for resisting colonialism and restoring one's cultures, identities, and histories.

Anti-colonial thought highlights the fundamental role of solidarity and collective resistance in the struggle against colonial domination. It emphasizes that solidarity, forged in a shared commitment to liberation, is necessary for challenging the hegemonic forces of colonialism (Dei & Asgharzadeh, 2001, p. 312). The collective action of oppressed groups, as highlighted by Lewis (2012), is essential for breaking both the psychological and material chains of colonization. Anti-colonial discourse provides a space where diverse marginalized groups, through collective struggle, can “come to voice” and assert their identity, challenging and dismantling the systems that seek to silence and subjugate them (Dei & Asgharzadeh, 2001, p. 317). As Mohanty (2003) further asserts, these collective struggles create new forms of activism rooted in a shared desire for emancipation and in opposition to both colonial and global capitalist systems of oppression. Amílcar Cabral's work echoes this sentiment, arguing that one of the main aims of anti-colonial resistance is the reclamation of a people's history, which had been

distorted or erased by colonial powers. Cabral asserts that the colonial powers did not bring the colonized into history but instead sought to sever them from their own historical trajectory, forcing them to follow the “progress” of the colonizers’ narrative (cited in Rabaka, 2014). By reclaiming their history and their future, colonized peoples reassert their autonomy, a process essential for true liberation (Doran, 2019).

4.2 Anti-Colonial, Post-Colonial, and Decolonial Thought

Simmons and Dei (2012) clarify that while anti-colonialism may draw on postcolonial and neo-colonial writings and theoretical stances, these frameworks and approaches are not the same. Elam (2019) defines postcolonial theory as “a body of thought primarily concerned with accounting for the political, aesthetic, economic, historical, and social impact of European colonial rule around the world in the 18th through the 20th century” (para 1). Although both the anti-colonial framework and postcolonial discourse serve as critical lenses for interrogating colonialism and its consequences, they differ in some key respects. One significant difference between the two lies in the meaning and implications of their prefixes. While the “anti” in anti-colonial refers to “fighting against colonial forces” (Nunn & Whetung 2020, p. 155), the “post” in postcolonial refers to the “aftermath of colonial occupation” (Gandhi, 1998, p. 4). Implicit in the prefix “post” is the belief that colonialism has ended. As Dei and Asgharzadeh (2001) express, the ‘post’ symbolizes an “unrealistic rupture... a break from the colonial past and a plunge into a different state of being... a post-colonial world” (p. 304).

Sawant (2012) states that post-colonialism refers to a historical event marked by terms like ‘after colonialism’, ‘after independence’, ‘after the end of empire’” (p. 120). On the other hand, anti-colonial scholars operate on the premise that colonialism “did not end with the return of political sovereignty to colonized peoples or nation states” (Dei and Kempf, 2006, p.2). They

assert that colonial relations should not be confined to traditional European or British colonialism but should encompass all forms of domination and oppression arising from power and privilege structures (Dei & Asgharzadeh, 2001). The limited definition offered by postcolonial theorization ignores the ongoing colonial realities faced by the majority of the world's population, especially those living under contemporary forms of domination such as neo-colonialism and ongoing imperialism.

Nunn and Whetung (2020) note that anti-colonialism is closely linked with decolonization, though they are not identical. Both are analytical tools for interrogating colonialism and its legacies, but they differ in some ways. Decolonization, as Dei and Asgharzadeh (2001) describe, is a process that questions the entire colonial system and its aftermath, aiming to change the social order. It is concerned with “undoing colonialism” while reimagining and reconstructing society, culture, and knowledge and creating a “new humanism” (Wynter, 2003). Decolonial projects, as Quijano suggests, involve a “delinking” from colonial epistemologies and the development of alternative ways of knowing and understanding the world. While anti-colonialism is primarily about actively resisting and opposing colonialism, decolonization focuses on the long-term process of creating a society that is free from colonial influence (Nunn & Whetung, 2020; Dei & Asgharzadeh, 2001). As Thiophene (1995) asserts, decolonization is not a final destination or an endpoint but an ongoing process (cited in Dei & Asgharzadeh, 2001, p. 298). In line with this thought, Dei and Asgharzadeh (2001) argue that anti-colonial actions are essential for decolonial projects.

4.3 Anti-Colonial Theory and Its Application to the Study

Anti-colonial discourse provides a critical framework for examining how colonial legacies and dominance persist in modern institutions like schools. As Wane (2006) notes, “Any

form of colonialism is bound to leave a mark of some kind” (p. 87). Certainly, it is not far-fetched to say that Jamaica, a country formally colonized by Spain and Great Britain, still bears traces of colonialism in all aspects of society, including in school policies. As Roofe (2024) confirms, Jamaica’s formal education system is modelled after the British colonizers’. An anti-colonial discursive framework is therefore useful for this study as it offers a tool for interrogating “the continuities and discontinuities of the colonial and neocolonial” (Dei and Kempf, 2006, p. 2), recognizing that colonialism’s impact is not just historical but ongoing and shaping attitudes toward race, culture, and identity in educational spaces. This framework also enables an intersectional analysis of race, class, sexuality, and gender in the context of colonial oppression (Dei, 2008; Akena, 2012). Additionally, anti-colonial discourse affirms Indigenous knowledge systems and ways of being, which are often suppressed or devalued by the colonial education system. Anti-colonialism is a framework that prioritizes the perspectives of local communities, focusing on their understanding of their own experiences and the multiple forms of oppression they endure (Simmons and Dei, 2012). Through this lens, I seek to critically assess how school grooming regulations reflect colonial attitudes and how colonialism continues to impact the experiences of students in Jamaican high schools.

Chapter 5

The Problematization of Natural Hair

5.1 Introduction

Ms. Anderson, the guidance counselor who helped recruit participants for this study, gestured toward a student standing on the porch. “Miss Brown, there’s Eva. She’s one of the students who wants to participate in the research. Her mother has signed the permission slip.” I nodded, approached Eva, and introduced myself, expecting a warm response. Instead, she shot me a look of suspicion and said, “Miss, wah mi a guh get out a dis?” [Miss, what am I going to get out of this?/How will I benefit from participating in the study?] The bluntness of her words caught me completely off guard. I paused for a moment before answering, “Nothing. This is just research I’m doing to complete my master’s degree.” Her gaze lingered on me – a mix of frustration, disappointment, and skepticism, as if she was hoping for something more from the conversation. I quickly added, “So, what would you like to get out of this?” Without missing a beat, Eva answered, “Miss, mi waan dem fi change d rules. Mi caan badda.” [Miss, I want them to change the rules. I am fed up.] Just as I was about to respond, another student rushed over, alerting Eva that it was time to head to class. The moment was over, but her initial question and response remained on my mind: What was behind Eva’s frustration?

When I finally had a chance to speak with Eva again, I asked, “Why do you want the school rules to change?” Her answer was more revealing than I had anticipated. She spoke carefully, but there was an unmistakable conflict in her words:

“I understand that the school has to have rules, but...”

“I understand that some hairstyles are not appropriate for school, but...”

“I understand that students will bend the rules, but...”

“I know some rules are protecting us, but...”

Each sentence was an attempt to reconcile what she supposedly understood about the need for rules with her deep discomfort with the school’s hair policy. Her response mirrored many other responses I would hear throughout the research, demonstrating how students navigate the tension between their interpretation of the policy and their desire to wear their natural hairstyles to school. The students, like Eva, often acknowledged that rules were crucial for “maintaining discipline” and for “preparing them for the work world.” However, they also recognized that the very rules designed to maintain discipline were, in many ways, unfair and deeply rooted in the colonial legacy of the school and of British colonization.

To gain a deep understanding of the students’ experience and their frustration with the school, it is essential that I first examine the policy document itself and how it frames natural hair and hair stylization. From my conversations with the students, it is clear that the underlying logic of the school rules is deeply embedded in their perceptions, which, in turn, significantly shapes their experiences with wearing natural hairstyles to school. To fully understand their frustration and internal conflict, we need to investigate the assumptions the policy is built upon – assumptions that the students consistently reference when discussing their own hair experiences. I will apply Bacchi’s WPR (What’s the Problem Represented to Be?) method to critically analyze the meanings that policy attaches to natural hairstyles and how those meanings shape the students’ perception of natural hair and their experience wearing natural hairstyles to school.

As previously articulated in Chapter 3 of this manuscript, the WPR method is predicated on the assertion that policy frameworks do not simply address pre-existing problems; rather, they actively construct and define the very nature of those problems (Bacchi, 2009). In other words,

policies function as mechanisms that shape problems in a particular way through their framing within the policy document and its subsequent implementation (Bacchi, 2019a). In interrogating the solutions proposed in the policy, it becomes imperative to pose some critical questions to uncover the explicit and implicit representations of the problem. These inquiries are conducted through an anti-colonial lens, which aims to unveil the colonial logic embedded within the policy texts and the construction of the problem — which is natural hair itself. Such an analytical framework aligns with the work of Dei and Asgharzadeh (2001), who assert that colonialism did not end with the return of political sovereignty to formerly colonized peoples or nation-states. The findings discussed here demonstrate that colonialism is not a foreign construct, but rather, a present reality that perpetuates anti-Black sentiments, in the form of natural hair-based discrimination, from Black administrators to Black students.

5.2 Outward Appearance – Inner Qualities?

During my initial conversation with three students, one of them pulled out the student handbook to quote the hair grooming policy. As they explained, the handbook is given to all students upon acceptance into the school so they can familiarize themselves with the rules before starting their academic journey at Sankofa High School. Students are expected to have the handbook with them at all times to easily reference it and know how to conform to the rules. This requirement, which mandates constant access to the handbook, reflects a broader system of control designed to regulate, monitor, and shape student behaviour in alignment with institutionalized norms. It signals to students that they cannot be trusted to navigate the academic environment without constant guidance from the institution. This requirement mirrors the colonial tactic of surveillance. As Foucault (1977) argues, modern systems of power increasingly rely on surveillance and self-discipline rather than overt punishment. In the case of Sankofa High

School, the system can be understood as a form of self-surveillance, where students internalize institutional rules and become complicit in their own regulation. Foucault's (1977) concept of the panopticon helps explain this process: power operates by encouraging individuals to monitor themselves, leading to self-discipline. By continually referencing the handbook, students are expected to participate in their own surveillance, ensuring conformity to the institutional expectations.

The rationale for the hair grooming policy provides the discursive justification that makes hair regulation appear necessary and serves to fuel conformity. Sankofa High School's hair grooming policy rationale reads:

There is much that can be assumed about an individual based on his/her physical appearance. Proper grooming indicates an outward expression of self-esteem and pride in how you look. Consequently, **ALL STUDENTS** who attend **[SANKOFA] HIGH SCHOOL** should be properly groomed and the dress code of the institution must be adhered to at **ALL TIMES**... Students will learn to practice acceptable behaviour, which will mould them for their future life in society. (Sankofa High School Handbook, 2024, p. 20)

I invoke the WPR method to delineate the motives and assumptions embedded in the policy rationale. Rather than accepting the policy rationale at face value, the WPR framework requires an analysis of how the "problem" is represented, what assumptions are hidden within its framing, and what forms of knowledge are mobilized to render it intelligible. This method invites a close reading of the policy language to scrutinize what is said, what is left unsaid, and what must be assumed in order for the rationale to appear reasonable.

In framing its rationale, the policy relies on the assumption that a student's outward appearance mirrors their internal qualities and character. Hence, within the context of this research, the policy suggests that the way students style and groom their hair reflects their character, self-discipline, and respect for self and others. With this assumption, the policy sets

guidelines for what counts as “proper grooming,” and the students who adhere to the hair grooming policy (which should be **ALL STUDENTS**) are of good moral character, have self-esteem and personal pride, and are capable of conforming to institutional expectations. By stating that “students will learn to practice acceptable behaviour which will mould them for their future life in society,” the policy constructs the idea that students’ hair grooming choices need to be regulated because they are directly tied to their future success. It suggests that failure to conform to hair grooming standards signifies a lack of essential qualities for success, thereby positioning students with certain hairstyles as needing correction and/or guidance. Essentially, the problem is represented as a lack of discipline in personal appearance, which the policy aims to address through “strict enforcement” of the school rules.

Discipline is a core value at Sankofa High School. The emphasis on discipline is embedded within the policy rationale and was consistently referenced in various contexts while I carried out my observation at the school. During a morning assembly, for instance, the vice-principal reminded students that “indiscipline is not tolerated at Sankofa High School.” The term “indiscipline” carries historical and cultural implications that cannot be overlooked. Blair (2023) notes that when she first encountered the term while teaching in Jamaica, she found it confusing. As she writes, “It seemed to reference any misbehaviour but was also related to race in ways that I was not familiar with in America” (p. 18). Winkler (1995) purports that indiscipline is a word that most Jamaicans equate with blackness. This connection between indiscipline and blackness is deeply rooted in Jamaica’s colonial past. Winkler (1995) further elaborates on this concept from a local cultural perspective, describing indiscipline as “unculturedness, and general ill-mannerliness” (p. 89). He states that indiscipline is a term rooted in the legacy of slavery, where blackness was historically associated with captivity and

barbarism. Whiteness, on the other hand, has been historically linked to civility, order, and moral superiority, often portrayed as the standard of discipline and societal normativity (D'Angelo, 2016; Goldberg, 1993, 2001). Interrogating the policy rationale from this perspective alerts us to the colonial assumption that is embedded in the grooming policy: Black physical appearance, including Black hair, is uncultured and in need of discipline.

The practice of associating indiscipline with blackness and discipline with whiteness reflects broader dichotomies that continue to reinforce racialized power structures in educational institutions. As Fanon (1961) states, the colonial world is a Manichean world, characterized by a dualistic worldview where the Europeans are seen as civilized and rational and Black people are viewed as uncivilized, barbaric and in need of control. This dualistic worldview, created by colonialism, placed Europeans in a position of superiority while deeming Black people inferior. Black bodies are stripped of their humanizing characteristics through this dehumanizing and violent process. White bodies are defined as “human,” and Black bodies are categorized as “not fully human” (Wynter, 2003). This dualistic racialization served to justify the atrocities of slavery and presented colonization as a “civilizing mission” (Fanon, 1961). Given that Black bodies, and by extension Black hair, are deemed uncivilized through a colonial lens, rules were created in schools to control and manage their presence.

The students themselves recognize that the policy frames Black natural hair as a problem to be regulated, controlled, and disciplined. As both Eva and Abigail remark, “[Sankofa High] is training us to be young ladies.” The term “lady,” when invoked within the local context, is heavily laden with gendered, classed, and racialized connotations. In Jamaica, a sharp divide exists between a “lady” and a “woman.” According to Lisa Douglass (1991), the term woman is often used to describe a working-class, dark-skinned female who is loud, aggressive, unruly, and

unfeminine. A “lady,” on the other hand, is of middle- or upper-class status, typically a white or brown female, educated, refined, soft-spoken, feminine, and does not use vulgar language (Douglass, 1991). Evidently, the Jamaican notion of class is mediated by race and other factors to differentiate between a lady and a woman. Both Stuart Hall and Eleanor J. Blair suggest that race and class are not fixed but performative, hence they are fluid categories marked with certain restrictions. Following this reasoning, a dark-skinned individual can attain the status of a “lady” by adopting the traits associated with this ideal. In this way, schools train girls to conform to a racial and class-based ideal of femininity through the enforcement of hair grooming standards.

The policy’s emphasis on grooming represents a cultural and institutional belief that hair, as a visible signifier of character, needs to be regulated to ensure that students embody traits like discipline and readiness for society. A closer examination of the cultural context of “discipline” reveals that a set of colonial logics are embedded within it. The notion of discipline is tied to race, class, and gender hierarchies that seek to control, tame, and regulate Black bodies. By tying “discipline” to whiteness, middle/upper-class status, and femininity, Black girls are forced to change their natural hair to fit the mould of “proper” and “appropriate” appearance for success. The racialized understanding of femininity demands that Black girls deny their Blackness and subject themselves to rules that link Black hair to negative character traits. The problem represented by the policy, then, is not simply about appearance or grooming – it is about the colonial power structures that define who belongs to the category of “human” and who does not. The grooming policy reinforces colonial racialized power structures that have constructed Blackness as uncultured, uncivilized, and in need of training and regulation. The enforcement of the hair grooming policy can then be described as a civilizing mission to discipline Black hair into “proper” colonial ideals of femininity.

5.3 No Fuzz - No Fuss?

Sankofa High School's grooming policy does not explicitly ban or single out natural hair or any particular natural hairstyle. It is framed as a 'neutral' policy, designed to apply uniformity to "ALL STUDENTS" regardless of ethnicity. However, this purported "neutrality" is complicated by the underlying implications of the policy and the way it is enforced. One administrator, Mr. Bob, tried to justify the policy rationale by stating, "No one has a problem with natural hair, it's the way the students carry themselves, the hairstyles they wear and the values attached to them." In this seemingly innocuous statement, Mr. Bob unwittingly reveals the policy's true purpose: to act as part of a civilizing mission – one that seeks to reshape students' appearances according to a narrow, prescribed standard of discipline and respectability. Mr. Bob points out that certain hairstyles carry implicit value judgments, with some being associated with positive or appropriate traits, while others are seen as embodying negative or unladylike qualities. This raises the question: Which hairstyles carry positive values and which do not?

While the policy itself refrains from naming specific hairstyles, its enforcement speaks volumes. Teachers and administrators frequently instruct students to modify their hairstyles, exposing the hidden biases embedded in the policy. Over time, students have come to recognize which hairstyles are targeted: Afros, Chiney bumps (Bantu knots), and high puffs. These styles are repeatedly flagged as "inappropriate," revealing a clear message that these hairstyles carry negative values and are inherently "unladylike" or unworthy of being worn on the school grounds. What makes this even more troubling is that these hairstyles are unique to Black people due to the natural characteristics of their hair. As Sherrow (2023) demonstrates, the very texture of Black natural hair allows for the formation of these styles in ways that chemically altered hair or straight hair cannot replicate. Additionally, students have noticed a striking disparity in policy

enforcement. They have observed that individuals with straight or chemically treated hair are rarely, if ever, asked to modify their hairstyles to meet the grooming standards. This shows that despite the absence of explicit reference to natural hair or natural hairstyles, the enforcement of the policy does not obscure its investment in framing Black hair as a problem to be corrected, disciplined, and controlled.

To better understand the scope of this problem, let us take a closer look at the specific language used in the policy to describe what is considered appropriate grooming and what is not. Here, I continue to apply the WPR approach through an anticolonial lens, probing the assumptions and power relations embedded in these definitions. Thinking problematically allows me to shift from accepting the policy's claims as given to interrogating how such "truths" are produced, what ideologies they rely on, and whose interests they serve. This examination will highlight the guidelines of the "civilizing mission," i.e., the training young Black girls undergo to become "respectable young ladies" as defined through the colonial lens. Sankofa High School's hair grooming policy states:

1. Hair must be neatly restrained at all times.
2. Hair ornaments should be small and should not exceed six pieces.
3. No artificial hair of any kind
4. No hair colouring
5. No beads, no bandeau, no headband, no showy hair ornaments

Each infraction is viewed as it relates to oneself and the school community at large. Any breach of the grooming policy will result in the student being sent to correct the uniform, receive a detention mark, or be suspended. Other possible actions include: sending for a parent/guardian or referring to a Guidance Counsellor. A written report will be placed in the student's file. (Sankofa High School Handbook, 2024, p. 20)

At first glance, the policy's general guidelines may appear to be "neutral" and universally applicable. However, a critical examination of the specific language used in the policy reveals its anti-Blackness and demonstrates how Black natural hair is disproportionately impacted. Here in this manuscript, I will start this problematization by examining the word "neat." I was curious to

learn the understanding of the word “neat” at Sankofa High, so I asked the students to share their perspectives. Their responses highlighted the conflict between the policy and the natural characteristics of their hair. They described “neat” hair as one in which all coiled tresses and individual strands are flattened and tucked away, leaving no loose hair visible. Brianna explained that neat hair is “not frizzy,” while Destiny elaborated that the “*neatness*” school administrators seek involves “getting the products in and ensuring that it [the strands] stays down.”

The Merriam-Webster Collegiate Dictionary (2025) describes frizzy hair as hair that is not smooth or orderly because the individual strands do not align together. Unlike straight or wavy hair, which tends to lie flat and uniform against the scalp, Black natural hair grows in tight coils, curls, or zig-zag patterns (Heva Clinic, 2025; Sherrow, 2023). These patterns naturally create volume and lift, causing the hair to expand outward and upward rather than lying flat. As Fallon notes, due to its natural characteristics and growth pattern, “curly/afro-textured hair is automatically assumed as fuzzy,” hence it must be altered or “tamed” to be perceived as proper for school.

By requiring girls to flatten and restrain their hair, the school sends the message that hair that grows upwards or outwards is inferior to hair that grows flat. In other words, Black natural hair is positioned as inferior to straight or chemically altered hair. As Tate (2017) suggests, the school rules dictate that Black hair needs to be “domesticated” to meet the school’s expectations (p. 99). This is an attempt to control Black girls’ bodies by forcing students to “reduce their Blackness into a more palatable state” (Brown, 2018, p. 74). This illustrates how racialized hierarchies and Eurocentric norms are perpetuated within a majority-Black population by Black individuals themselves. Drawing on the work of Frantz Fanon (1952), I describe this imposition as a form of internalized inferiority. Fanon describes Black folks as “people in whose soul an

inferiority complex has been created” (p. 18). He explains that colonized people internalize an “inferiority complex,” where they are made to believe that their ways of life are primitive or unworthy compared to the colonizer’s culture (Fanon, 1952, p. 18). This internalized inferiority is passed down from one generation to the next and erases cultural identity in an attempt to emulate whiteness, which is positioned as superior.

The imposition of colonial hair ideals is particularly damaging to students, both psychologically and physically. Mercer (1987) points out that hair is the most visible marker of Black identity next to skin; therefore, when schools demand that students restrain or alter their natural hair, they are, in effect, erasing black identity. This “erasure of Black presence from socio-political and aesthetic life” is rooted in the “dissection of Black bodies,” where Black natural features are judged, devalued, and forced into conformity with Eurocentric standards (Tate, 2017, p. 99). Hair grooming policies remind students that Black natural hair falls low on the scale of beauty while affirming Eurocentric, hegemonic beauty paradigms (Prince, 2009). Therefore, when Black students are told their hair is a violation of school rules, it is not just a condemnation of their physical appearance. Undoubtedly, it is a rejection of their racial identity. Tate (2017) asks, “What must it be like for your hair to be described as a ‘violation’ when you yourself, your bodily integrity, your racial identity as shown through your hair are violated by taunts and school rules?” (p. 98). The psychological toll of this violence is immense, as it forces children to internalize the idea that they are somehow less worthy, less beautiful, and less deserving of acceptance simply because of how their hair naturally grows (Mbilishaka & Apugo, 2020; Nkimbeng et al., 2023). This contempt is a form of psychic violence that damages students’ sense of self-worth and makes it difficult to navigate a world that continually devalues their natural identity.

The students at Sankofa High express their frustration with the challenge of keeping their hair “neatly restrained,” a task that sometimes feels impossible to achieve. To attain a “flattened” and “neat” appearance, many students rely on creams, gels, grease, and other styling products to smooth their hair and hold it in place. While sitting under a tree, one student with short afro-textured hair shared her daily struggle to meet this requirement. She explained that she must use a significant amount of gel and secure her hair with a headwrap overnight to keep the strands flattened and “neat.” Yet, despite her best efforts, before the end of the school day, her hair begins to “frizz out,” betraying her attempts to flatten it. Her recurring battle is met with the harsh criticism of teachers, who frequently ask, “Why don’t you comb your hair?” As if her natural coils were a problem. Her loose, uneven strands become a point of judgment. Another student chimed in and said, “Dat’s y mi jus cream mi hair. Mi hair too short fi ketch up r duh slick back, an mi caan bodda wid dem a tell mi fi fix it.” [“That’s why I relax my hair. My hair is too short to put my hair up in a ponytail or do a slick back hairdo, moreover, I can’t be bothered with them telling me to fix it.”]

The physical effects of altering Black natural hair to fit colonial hegemonic standards of beauty and femininity are numerous. The use of chemicals and heat to straighten or flatten hair results in burns, physical pain, hair disorders, and elevated risks of other illnesses (Anderson, 2020; Donahoo & Smith, 2022). Recent studies also reveal that the use of hair products in the Black community exposes individuals to endocrine-disrupting chemicals, some associated with adverse health outcomes, including breast cancer (James-Todd et al., 2021; Fillon, 2017). In addition, the use of chemicals or even wearing hairstyles that restrain the hair can result in hair breakage and hair loss. Dupes and Sandeen (2024) explain that styles such as ponytails, buns, and slick-backs can exert excessive tension on the hair shafts, leading to hair and scalp disorders.

The students at Sankofa High often wear buns and slickback hairstyles because when the coily strands are flattened and tucked away, their hair is less likely to be viewed as a violation of the school rules. Many students at Sankofa High have observed detrimental effects on their hair health as a consequence of regularly wearing these restrictive styles. To mitigate this, Destiny and her friends have chosen to avoid restraining their hair outside of school in an effort to preserve its health.

Students have also experienced headaches from wearing hairstyles intended to maintain a flat and neat appearance. One day, I noticed Eva sitting quietly in the library, her hair unbound. The imprint of her hair tie was a silent testament to the effort she had put into restraining her short, afro-textured hair. Curiously, I asked why she had removed the hair tie. Eva explained that she was experiencing a headache. As she spoke, it became clear that the constant pressure to keep her hair restrained was a physical burden and a source of discomfort. She shared that she often experiences headaches whenever she attempts to put her hair up. In search of relief, she would often sneak away to quiet corners, removing her hair tie to escape the constant strain. Eva expressed a deep yearning to let her hair flow freely, unbound by the expectations imposed upon her by the grooming policy. She wished for a world where her hair was not problematic, where the natural state of her hair would not be seen as untidy but as an expression of who she truly is. When her hair is unrestrained, Eva noted, the headaches vanish. So she removes the hair tie because it offers a brief reprieve from the physical and emotional weight of conforming to the socially constructed definition of “neat” hair. But once she returns to the purview of the administrators, teachers, and students, Eva is back under the surveillance of the colonial gaze.

5.4 Where are the silences?

The idea that straight, flat, shiny hair is “neat,” while curly/coily hair is deemed untidy and must be restrained or altered to be “proper,” raises critical questions about the origins and persistence of these hair grooming norms. Why has Sankofa High School adopted the practice of regulating hair? Who defines what is neat? What is left unproblematic in the Sankofa High School hair grooming policy? Abigail firmly believes that “It comes from colonization. It comes from colorism, it comes from classism, it comes from racism, which is engraved in us as Black people... It’s deeper than just the surface.” Abigail is incisive and deeply attuned to the colonial underpinnings of the policy. Her reading unsettles the common assumption that students are unaware of the power structures that shape their schooling. Her assessment leads us beyond surface-level interpretations of “neatness” and “discipline” to the deeper structures of domination and the afterlives of official colonization.

Firstly, the perception that Black hair in its natural coily or curly state is untidy and in need of regulation is not a neutral or naturally occurring judgment. It is a social construct shaped by centuries of colonial oppression, racial discrimination, and hegemonic violence. This mindset traces back to Western colonization. Colonial powers imposed physical violence on Black bodies and promoted rigid beauty standards. European features were glorified, while others were dehumanized to justify the violence of slavery. Historical records show that there was no negative perception of Black hair prior to colonization. This historical fact further highlights how the perception of natural curly or coily hair as untidy and in need of regulation is socially constructed through colonial dominance.

As demonstrated by scholars such as Banks (2021), Byrd & Tharps (2014), Johnson & Bankhead (2014), Sherrow (2023), and Sieber & Herreman (2000), Black natural hair in

pre-colonial African communities was a beautiful and rich expression of cultural identity and pride. However, colonial powers used legal, social, and psychological means to impose Eurocentric standards and devalue African culture and beauty. Scientific racism served as a tool of domination, reinforcing a racial hierarchy that positioned Blackness as inferior to the European norm. Under colonial rule, Black hair was often subjected to legal regulations as a form of racialized control and subjugation. As Johnson & Bankhead (2014) point out, enslaved Africans' hair was forcibly cut off before they were taken to the Americas. When they arrived in the West, Africans could no longer practice their hairstyling culture, instead, they were forced to abide by hair regulations for the very first time.

Evidently, there is nothing inherently negative about Black natural hair. Black curls and coils are neither untidy nor messy – they are beautiful. Therefore, when schools implement policies that imply that Black students should flatten and restrain their coils and curls for their hairstyles to be considered “proper” for school, those policies cannot be described as neutral. The policies are built on a colonial logic that should be eradicated. We should remember that before European colonization, Black hair in Africa was celebrated for its beauty and cultural significance. Black hairstyles were works of art, rich with meaning and positive symbolism. They were free from the white gaze and without restrictions. It was the Europeans who altered the narratives, perceptions, and treatment of Black hair as a means to exert power and control over Black folks.

Today, even in the absence of official colonial powers, these colonial constructs of beauty and civility persist. The school administrators, despite being Black, are not exempt from the pervasive influence of colonialism. They have internalized the very standards of whiteness that once sought to oppress them. Even the students are not blinded by the facade of a “post-colonial

independent Jamaica.” As Eva points out, “the school was originally founded by a white person and was exclusively for white males. Even after it became co-educational and later admitted Black students, the institution struggled to let go of its colonial roots.” Eva’s observation aligns with Morrison and Milner’s (1995) argument that post-independence Jamaica retained the structure and logic of the British colonial education system. Formal sovereignty did not remove the aesthetic codes that excluded and subordinated Black people. As Thompson (2025) contends, colonialism is not a historical moment but a transhistorical phenomenon, persisting in shifting and often covert forms across time and space.

Fallon also reflects on the coloniality of the school policies, noting, “In our mainly Black country, I understand that [Sankofa] High School was originally made for white people, but the times have changed.” Eva opined that the school’s administrators, by adhering to these outdated practices, are trying to preserve the legacy of Adam Johnson (pseudonym), the school’s founder, who was likely a slave owner. The refusal to reimagine these policies for a majority-Black student population is a form of ideological fidelity and a commitment to the “ongoing legacies of colonial racism [that] shape [the] educational inequality and discrimination” of Afro-Jamaican children (Thompson, 2025, p. 11). When I asked students what changes they would like to see in the school rules around hair, they all named the Afro and Chiney Bumps (also known as Bantu Knots) as hairdos that should be permitted at Sankofa High School. They assert that these hairstyles are symbols of cultural pride and African identity, hence, they should be celebrated, not suppressed.

5.5 The Afro Hairstyle

The Afro, as described by Dash (2006), is “a style that draws on qualities intrinsic to curly African hair: the coil of the hair [and] its capacity to grow in a thick mass” (Dash, 2006, p.

32). The Afro's distinctive round shape is not something that can be easily replicated by those with looser hair textures, straight hair, or chemically altered hair. These textures simply cannot achieve the same form as they do not possess the necessary tightness or natural curls to maintain the round shape of an Afro. This makes the hairstyle unique to Black individuals. Although the policy does not explicitly list the Afro as a prohibited style, its requirement that hair be "restrained" effectively bans the Afro. Meanwhile, students with straight hair are allowed to wear their hair loose without penalty. This disparity points to implicit biases embedded in the policy's enforcement, and leaves us to question whether deeper, unspoken rationales are at work in this exclusionary practice. Drawing on Mr. Bob's statement that hairstyles carry implicit value assumptions, I will examine the implicit assumptions and the underlying logic that may inform the school administrators' perceptions of Afro hairstyles.

I posit that the Afro hairstyle continues to carry a complex set of meanings that have been shaped by colonial resistance and white supremacist perceptions. As outlined in Chapter 2 of this manuscript, the Afro was popularized in the 1960s by the Black Panther Party, one of several organizations within the broader Black Power movement, which originated in the United States and later spread to countries such as Jamaica. Like the Black Panther Party, Afros became a visual representation of the rejection of white supremacy. Afros were framed as a symbol of radicalism, rebellion, extremism, and unruliness in an effort to suppress the Black Power Movement (Mercer, 2000). Many in mainstream white society viewed the Black Panthers and other Black Power groups negatively, fearing that they would rise up against their oppressors and disrupt the colonial order (Berger, 1991; Pruitt, 2020).

The fear of the Black Power Movement also spread to Jamaica. In *Groundings with My Brothers*, Walter Rodney sheds light on the Jamaican government's deep fear of Black Power

ideologies during this time. He recalls how the government moved swiftly to suppress the growing tide of radical Black consciousness, going so far as to ban Rodney himself from the island in 1968. Rodney calls the government “white-hearted Black men,” stating that the government “serves the interests of a foreign, white capitalist system” and upholds a “social structure which ensures that the Black man resides at the bottom of the social ladder” (Rodney, 2019, pp. 30, 63). It is through this same lens, whether consciously or unconsciously, that the Afro continues to be read in Jamaica. These negative imagery attached to these anti-colonial resistance movements linger, and there continue to be “white-hearted” administrators who sustain a colonial education system that perpetuates white values.

The school administration offers a different set of reasons for banning Afro. Brianna, Eva, and Fallon mentioned that they were told that Afro is not a hairstyle for school because “it does not fit the uniform.” Brianna adds that students are encouraged to wear hairstyles that do not seem “outrageous or outlandish for school.” Fallon said that some of her friends wore Afros to school and were told that the hairstyle was not allowed because it was too distracting. The students were instructed to use a hair tie to put their hair up. These comments from administrators reflect Mercer’s findings that for many Black folks who have been socialized to see straight hair as ideal, Afros seem extreme and “unpalatable” (Mercer, 2000, p. 62).

The other students in the study mentioned that they have never worn an Afro to school but have had lots of conversations with school friends about wishing they could wear the hairdo. In fact, the student council body at Sankofa High School lobbied to have an “Afro Day” at school. An Afro Day would be one day out of the entire school year when the students are allowed to wear the Afro hairstyle to school. The purpose of Afro Day was to raise awareness about the beauty and significance of Afro-textured hair and to challenge the stigma of Black hair

as “nappy.” Eva said, “A lot of people wanted it [the Afro Day] to happen.” The school administration granted the students permission to have the Afro Day, but the permission was later reneged with no specific reason given. Despite the good intentions behind Afro Day and the positive outcomes students anticipated, Afro Day was never allowed to proceed, even two years later. The Afro hairstyle continues to be seen as a hairstyle that is not “proper” for school. Destiny does not believe that the school will ever allow students to wear Afros to school because “to them [the school administration], the Afro is messy.”

5.6 Chiney Bumps/Bantu Knots

Figure 5.1

Chiney Bumps/Bantu Knots Hairstyle

Note. Photo of a student in Trinidad who the school principal warned not to wear the natural hairstyle. Schools across the Caribbean have strict hair grooming policies.

Source. Moore, S. (2019) -Trinidad and Tobago Newsday.

The hairstyle known as Bantu Knots or Chiney Bumps (as we call it in Jamaica) is a traditional hairstyle originating from the Zulu people of southern Africa (Obaizamomwan-Hamilton, 2024). The style involves sectioning the hair into small parts, twisting each section, and then wrapping the twisted sections into tight knots close to the scalp. Bantu knots can vary in size and number depending on how the individual chooses to style them. It is typically considered simple and neat, yet Chiney Bumps are not allowed at Sankofa High School. Destiny recalls one of her classmates wearing Chiney Bumps to school, and a teacher “stopped her at the gate and told her to take them out.” The students do not understand why Chiney Bumps are not allowed. The hair is neatly restrained; it does not require any hair ornaments, and it does not seem to violate any of the guidelines of the hair grooming policy. This calls to mind a prior news report in which a school principal justified the banning of Bantu knots by describing them as “dramatic” and “elaborate” (Jamaica Gleaner, 2021). The language used in this justification thinly veils anti-Black discourse. It compelled me to consider whether similar logics were at play at Sankofa High, and whether such bans rest on deeper, unspoken assumptions about the visibility of Blackness within formal educational spaces.

Eva believes that there is some discomfort with hairstyles that stem from our African heritage. “These hairstyles often remind Jamaicans of slavery, which they are trying to distance themselves from.” Eva’s observation is consistent with the findings of Mwakikagile (2023), whose research explores the relationships within the African diaspora, particularly between Africans, African Americans, and Afro-Caribbeans. Mwakikagile writes, “Some people in the African diaspora want to distance themselves from Africa and anything explicitly African... so much so that they would rather have come from anywhere, even from the forests and caves of Europe” (p. 64). Bourne et al. (2014) notes that the African hairdos are labelled as “vulgar and

disorderly,” hence the banning of many African-related hairstyles in certain settings in Jamaica (p. 134). This distancing from African heritage, which Mwakikagile discusses, is a direct consequence of the internalized anti-Black sentiments of colonialism and slavery. Tate (2022) describes this as the coloniality of aesthetics, stating that negative perceptions of African features are deeply rooted in colonial ideals that continue to influence modern-day attitudes and beliefs that African cultural practices are somehow less desirable.

At Sankofa High School, the students have expressed a desire to reconnect with their African identity, particularly through the rediscovery of cultural practices like hairstyling. Both Eva and Abigail shared their limited knowledge of pre-slavery African hairstyling traditions, expressing a strong desire to learn more about their African heritage within the school context. Fallon remarks, “I learned about how the Africans came to Jamaica, but we don’t really learn about Africa.” This gap in their education reflects a broader issue and the need to reinforce the fact that African history does not begin with the Transatlantic Slave Trade. As Walter Rodney (2019) eloquently argues, “Africans in the West have been deliberately kept ignorant of African achievements by the white man for centuries. The purpose of this policy was to build up a picture of a barbarous Africa, so that we Africans who had been removed from our homes and made into slaves would be afraid to admit even to ourselves that we were Africans” (p. 33). I submit that there is nothing inherently wrong with Chiney Bumps, Afros, or any other Black hairstyle. Banning these hairstyles in schools is an act of adhering to colonial logic, which erases Black identity and culture.

Compounding the issue of banning hairstyles tied to African roots is the unequal enforcement of hair policies based on texture rather than style. Students have observed that two individuals may enter the school campus wearing the same hairstyle, yet one is asked to change

their hairdo while the other is allowed to keep it, with no violation of school rules. The students are clear about the reason: it is texturism. Those with looser-textured hair are permitted to wear styles that students with tighter curls are not allowed to wear. This inconsistency exposes the underlying bias that it is not just hairstyles being judged, but the very texture of hair itself.

5.7 Texturism

Black natural hair is incredibly diverse and does not follow a monolithic texture. It comes in all shapes, colours, and patterns, each unique to the person it belongs to. According to Sherrow (2023), Black hair can range from thin to thick and from nearly straight to tightly coiled curls. Following the colonial logic of colour hierarchies, a hierarchy of textures that favours looser hair over kinkier hair has emerged. This social structure has led to a phenomenon known in Black communities as texturism – a form of discrimination that privileges individuals with looser curls or straighter hair over those with more tightly coiled hair. Texturism is often viewed as an extension of colorism, with both phenomena rooted in similar systems of intra-racial discrimination (Ellington, 2023; Kelly, 2024; Tate, 2025). Novelist Alice Walker, credited with coining the term colorism in her 1983 book *In Search of Our Mother's Gardens*, defines colourism as “prejudicial and preferential treatment of same-race people based on their colour” (Walker, 2004, p. 290). In much the same way, texturism operates as a form of bias that gives preferential treatment to hair textures that appear closer to whiteness and inadvertently marginalizes individuals with tighter coils or kinkier hair.

The roots of texturism and colorism are deeply planted in the colonial history of the Caribbean. These biases were not born out of natural differences but were manufactured to maintain a racial hierarchy constructed by the colonizers. As Mercer (2000) notes, the colonizers devised a system of pigmentocracy, upon which skin colour would determine one's labour and

socio-economic standing. During slavery, lighter-skinned Black individuals – often the offspring of enslaved African women and White slave owners through rape (Roberts, 2010, White, 2023) – were sometimes afforded privileges that darker-skinned individuals were not. Lighter-skinned enslaved people often worked in the enslaver’s house, performing tasks that were seen as less physically demanding. They sometimes had access to better food, clothing, and living conditions. Meanwhile, the darker-skinned enslaved individuals laboured under the harshest conditions in the fields. The physical divide between lighter-skinned enslaved people and darker-skinned ones mirrored the psychological and societal divide, which linked proximity to Whiteness with higher status, intelligence, and beauty (Brown, Ward, Lightbourn, & Jackson, 1999; Keith & Herring, 1991). In tandem with this, the looser curls commonly found in lighter-skinned and ‘mixed-race’ Black individuals’ hair were perceived as closer in texture to White people’s hair and, therefore, more desirable. This association between straighter, looser hair and higher social status reinforced the falsely constructed notion that hair resembling that of White people was inherently superior.

The end of slavery did not mark the end of these discriminatory practices; in fact, they persisted in more covert and internalized ways in Black communities. The phrases “good hair” and “bad hair” took root in Black communities, continuing the divide. “Good hair” referred to hair that was loose, wavy, or straight, while “bad hair” was used to describe hair that was thick and tightly coiled (Banks, 2000; Byrd & Tharps, 2001; Mercer, 1987). In Jamaica, the terms “pretty hair” and “dry head” mirror the “good hair” versus “bad hair” dichotomy, reflecting a broader cultural divide that shapes perceptions of beauty and self-worth. Although these terms denigrate Black hair, they are often used in Black households. Byrd and Tharps (2001) note that relatives would inspect a newborn and speculate about the texture of the hair that would cover

the baby's head. Parents use phrases such as "I hope my baby keeps her 'good' hair. It lays down so nice and is so slick and soft" (Ellington, 2023, p. 39). It was not unusual for a parent to express relief or pride if a child inherited "good hair." Parents, often unknowingly, instill these distinctions and the social value attached to hair texture in their children. The subconscious message was clear: straight hair was better, and kinky, coily hair was a problem to be solved or hidden. hooks (1989) describes the covert operation of texturism in Black communities, stating;

Good hair is hair that is not kinky, hair that does not feel like balls of steel wool, hair that does not take hours to comb, hair that does not need tons of grease to untangle, hair that is long. Real good hair is straight hair, hair like white folks' hair. Yet no one says so. No one says your hair is so nice, so beautiful because it is like white folks' hair. We pretend that the standards we measure our beauty by are our own invention. (p. 382)

The students at Sankofa High School are acutely aware of texturism and how it manifests itself at the school. Destiny says the texturism is "as clear as day," and Abigail adds that it is obvious that "they [the school administrators] are mainly targeting 4C hair." "4C" refers to a designation of hair texture based on the Andre Walker Hair Typing System, which categorizes hair textures based on curl patterns (see Figure 5.2). In this system, as explained by Blay (2021), hair is classified into a series of types and subtypes ranging from straight (Type 1) to wavy (Type 2), curly (Type 3), and coily (Type 4). The letters A, B, and C further categorize the hair type by describing the looseness or tightness of the curl, as well as how much volume and frizz it might have (Blay, 2021). According to Byrd and Tharps (2001), most Black women fall into the 3B to 4C categories. Sherrow (2023) states that about 75 percent of Black people have hair labelled kinky or spiralled.

Figure 5.2

Andre Walker Hair Typing System

Note. The Andre Walker Hair Typing System, a classification chart developed to categorize hair textures from straight (Type 1) to coily (Type 4).

Source. Blay, 2021

The students have noticed that it is primarily those with type 4 hair who are targeted by the school administrators. As Fallon shares, “I have this friend, I think she’s [a mixed-race] Dominican with loose curls, and her hair is completely loose, no hair ties, and she can say hi to the Dean of Discipline⁵ and everything. But if me, with my Afro-textured hair, did that, I would be penalized. I think it is ridiculous.” The students strongly believe that it is unfair and emotionally distressing to know that looser-textured hair is exempt from scrutiny while those with tightly coiled hair are often penalized for their hair texture. Destiny comments that the hair typing vocabulary is too problematic and divisive, so she avoids using it. Byrd and Tharps (2014) note that the divisiveness and hostility over the texture of natural hair is something many Black people experience. The stories shared by the students at Sankofa High corroborate this

⁵ The dean of discipline is a school administrator responsible for overseeing and managing the disciplinary process in a school.

point. They often hear schoolmates comparing girls in friend groups. “Haven’t you noticed that your friend has ‘pretty hair’ while your hair is so ugly?” students often say. Abigail shares that she faces harsh criticisms about her 4C hair nearly every day. “Fi yuh hair dry and tough.” “Trashy and fava basket.” These comments translated as “Your hair is dry and tough” and “Your hair is trashy, and it resembles a basket made from bushes” illustrate the internalized belief that kinky hair is like bushes: short, uncultivated, and undesirable. Both Abigail and Destiny used the words “sad” and “depressing” to describe how they feel about the unequal treatment.

Furthermore, the rules teach students to internalize these hair texture divisions, thereby shaping the “subjective positions” individuals are influenced to accept based on the way a problem is framed in policy (Bacchi, 2019b, 51:50). In *Black Skin, White Masks*, Fanon describes how colonized subjects come to view themselves through the colonizer’s gaze, often developing a “racial epidermal schema” that dictates self-worth according to proximity to whiteness (p. 112). This “epidermalization” of inferiority reveals how colonial imposition operates psychologically by instilling a sense of otherness and self-devaluation. At Sankofa High, the epidermalization Fanon speaks of is not contingent upon the presence of white bodies but is sustained through institutional practices that sediment colonial logics in the everyday lives of the students. What emerges is a form of alienation wherein students learn to read their natural textures as problems to be corrected or erased, and deploy defence mechanisms when their position on the racial schema is called out. This is evident when students try to downplay or mask their hurt from hair shaming with responses such as “mi know mi head dry - suh wah?” [I already know I have ‘bad hair,’ so why does it matter?] Yet, they proceed to texturize their hair, i.e., to use a chemical process that loosens tight curl patterns without fully straightening it (Sandeem, 2024).

This subjectification is also evident when students gloat about their mixed or “coolie” heritage. “Coolie” is a term used in Jamaica to describe a person of Indian heritage, often of mixed Indian and African descent (JP Linguistics, 2025). While Merriam-Webster (2025) traces the English word to the Hindi and Urdu *kūli/qulī*, meaning an unskilled labourer hired for subsistence wages, its colonial deployment carried dehumanizing connotations. As Breman and Daniel (1992) note, the term appears as early as 1581 in a letter that distinguishes between “men” and “coolies,” signaling a racialized hierarchy in which coolies were imagined as less than human (p. 269). Following the abolition of slavery in the British Empire, colonial powers turned to indentured labour to fill the economic void, importing workers from India to toil under harsh conditions in plantations across the Caribbean. These workers, labeled as “coolies,” endured a form of “voluntary slavery” and the negative meanings associated with the word coolie persisted in the Caribbean (Damir-Geilsdorf et al., 2016, p. 13). Over time, the meaning of “coolie” shifted in Jamaica. While it remains rooted in this violent history of colonialism and racialization, the term is now used colloquially to describe someone with “good hair,” often implying softer textures associated with mixed-race Indian ancestry. Hence, when a student brags about being a coolie, they are exerting their position on the racial schema while distancing themselves from Blackness. These experiences reflect the persistence of colonial beauty standards, where phenotypical proximity to whiteness is valorized and African features are disparaged.

5.8 Conclusion

Sankofa High School’s hair grooming policy seems non-discriminatory when read at face value, however, the enforcement reveals that the end of formal colonial rule did not mark the end of colonialism. Colonial logics continue to shape the everyday practices of educational

institutions in Jamaica, embedded in the mundane routines of schooling and discipline. The rule mandates that hair be restrained, yet, in practice, only students with Afro-textured hair are forced to abide by that rule. The definition of neat is laden with anti-Black sentiments, which demand that natural kinks and coils be suppressed, hidden, or altered to be considered proper grooming. Imposing bans on hairstyles linked to anti-colonial movements and African roots sends a clear message that schools remain invested in maintaining the racial hierarchy that serves the interests of the colonizers.

The assumptions and logic used to justify the grooming policies reveal a pattern of colonial continuity. The rationale that students are judged based on their outward appearance may be true, but what is left unspoken in the policy is that these judgements are based on colonial logic, where Blackness is silently tied to notions of indiscipline, and whiteness to ideals of femininity and respectability. In this regard, Black girls are made to feel as though their natural Afro-textured hair does not belong in schools. Students feel pressured to use chemicals or loads of hair products to alter or “tame” the texture of their natural hair. In the end, the students are left with psychological harm taking shape through feelings of shame, hyper-awareness of the body, anxiety, and internalization of inferiority. The physical and health impacts of these hair policies are also evident, with students reporting headaches that impede their focus at school and hair breakage.

Many students have recognized that the policies governing their hair carry the residue of colonial rule. They understand that they are in a school built to serve white boys and exclude Black life entirely. Though the institution now serves a predominantly Black student body and is led by Black administrators, the foundational ideologies have not changed, and its administrators continue to perpetuate the same systems of subjugation that were originally imposed on them.

Homi Bhabha's concept of colonial mimicry — “almost the same, but not quite” — helps explain how people who were once excluded by colonial systems can end up reinforcing those same systems. Bhabha (2021) describes mimicry as the way colonized subjects imitate the language, behaviour, and values of the colonizer. But this imitation is always incomplete and slightly different, revealing both the desire to belong and the impossibility of full acceptance (Bhabha, 2021). Like Fanon's (1952) Antillean subject who perfects the colonizer's language to be accepted by the white man, these Black school administrators uphold policies to signal their proximity to colonial notions of civility.

Students understand this reality. They feel the weight of policies that continue to frame their natural hair as undisciplined and problematic. Abigail calls out colonialism. Destiny names it “retention from slavery.” All the young girls indict the school for preserving the legacy of a slave owner. In naming the knowledge systems that underpin the hair grooming policy, students are demanding a change. They are calling for the dismantling of colonial policies and imagining possibilities for Black life (Evans-Winters & Love, 2015; Kelly, 2022). Their imagination invokes Afrofuturism (see Eshun, 2003 and Jenkins, 2021). They imagine Black life as anticipatory (McKittrick, 2013) and a refusal to accept the world as it is now. These students long for a school where Black girls are affirmed in their natural state, where femininity is not defined by colonial ideals, and where policy becomes a tool of care rather than control.

Chapter 6

Hair Joy

6.1 Introduction

Una Marson: “Kinky Hair Blues” (1937)

Gwine find a beauty shop Cause I ain't a belle.
Gwine find a beauty shop Cause I ain't a lovely belle.

The boys pass me by,
They say I's not so swell.

See oder young gals
So slick and smart.
See dose oder young gals
So slick and smart.

I jes gwine die on de shelf,
If I don't mek a start.

I hate dat ironed hair
And dat bleaching skin.
Hate dat ironed hair
And dat bleaching skin.

But I'll be all alone,
If I don't fall in.

Lord 'tis you did gie me
All dis kinky hair.
'Tis you did gie me
All dis kinky hair,
And I don't envy gals
What got dose locks so fair.

I like me black face
And me kinky hair.
I like me black face
And me kinky hair.

But nobody loves dem,
I jes don't tink it's fair.

Now I's gwine press me hair
And bleach me skin.

I's gwine press me hair
And bleach me skin.
What won't a gal do
Some kind of man to win.

Una Marson's 1937 poem *Kinky Hair Blues* captures the struggle of embracing one's natural kinky hair while grappling with the beauty ideals that demand conformity. Marson stands on the precipice of a decision, torn between her love for her 'black face' and 'kinky hair' and the societal pressure to adopt a 'slick and smart' appearance. Despite her love for her natural hair and her disdain for the hot iron, she ultimately chooses to press her hair, succumbing to the forces of expectation. This internal conflict is a story many Black girls and women can relate to, especially when attending schools with policies that pressure them to "restrain" their coily tresses. Needless to say, Black women and girls have never passively succumbed to colonial aesthetic demands; instead, they have been actively resisting for centuries. As Professor Dip Kapoor often reminds his students, "oppression breeds resistance." In other words, the very systems designed to dominate and control Black bodies often spark movements and counter-discourses aimed at reclaiming power and agency (Fanon, 1961; Gandhi, 1998).

Drawing from an anti-colonial perspective, resistance is understood as actions, both subtle and overt, through which marginalized agencies (individuals or groups) "have an impact on power" and challenge societal norms (Richmond, 2011). As I alluded to in Chapter 2, there are numerous examples of how Black hair has been disparaged. There are also accounts of how it has been reclaimed as a form of resistance throughout Western colonial history. During the Transatlantic Slave Trade, for instance, African people's hair was forcibly cut as a means of stripping them of their identity (Banks, 2021; Johnson & Bankhead, 2014; Ngandu-Kalenga Greensword, 2022). However, as Carney (2004) explains, African women found ways to conceal

rice grains in their children's hair, preserving a link to their heritage and culture, which later contributed to rice cultivation in the Americas. Additionally, the enslaved people used the intricate patterns of their cornrow hairdo to map escape routes (Quampah et al., 2023). These instances highlight how hair can become a site of resistance against colonial domination, a reclamation of identity, and a refusal to accept the dehumanization of Black bodies.

The resistance against colonial imposition continues today, as I will demonstrate in the case of Sankofa High School. Although the school grooming policy pushes Black girls to conform to Eurocentric ideals of hair grooming, the students at Sankofa High are pushing back. This chapter will explore hair joy as a form of anti-colonial resistance and a way of being. Hair joy is framed as a rejection of the colonial hierarchies of aesthetics that have historically dictated grooming standards and have relegated Afro-textured hair as something to be disciplined, controlled, or altered. This analysis is grounded in the understanding that beauty is racialized and politically constructed (Tate, 2010; Taylor, 1999). Therefore, finding freedom and pride in wearing one's natural hair becomes both a personal choice and a political statement. Drawing on Akena's (2012) argument that counter-discourses are essential for resisting domination, I highlight how the natural hair movement is growing, with a new generation of naturals embracing kinky hair as the norm. I examine the collective efforts of the students at Sankofa High School in resisting colonial grooming policies, reflecting on Dei & Asgharzadeh's (2001) argument that anti-colonial thought emphasizes the importance of solidarity and collective resistance in this struggle. As Lewis (2012) asserts, collective action is key to breaking free from the psychological and material chains of colonization. It is this journey of resistance, agency, self-acceptance, and pride that this chapter seeks to explore.

6.2 Rocking natural hair

I arrived at Sankofa High School early on a Monday morning to observe the types of hairstyles the students wore to school. I stood on the walkway, watching students as they entered the school premises. A teacher and one of the vice principals stood sentinel, greeting the students as they passed. Some students were stopped and instructed to rectify their uniforms. “Young man, why do you have a towel in your hand? Put it in your bag.” “Young lady, you have the wrong colour clip in your hair. You know you should not wear that to school.” “Sasha, your socks are too high. Pull them down.” The students had to correct their attire before they could go any further on the campus. Certainly, proper grooming and appropriate attire are important values at Sankofa High School, and students are expected to demonstrate these values upon entering the premises.

As I stood on the walkway observing the students, I was struck by how much time had changed since I last visited a high school in Jamaica 5 years ago. This time around, more students were wearing their natural hair. I made my way to the auditorium, where the students congregated for their morning assembly. They stood in lines according to their classes — for each class, boys in one line and girls in the other. When the morning assembly ended, they exited class by class, one line at a time. That was the perfect opportunity for me to do a quick head count. As the students passed by, I silently began tallying the number of girls with natural hair, and it became clear: it was easier to count those with chemically altered hair. In each class of 15 to 20 girls, I noted an average of 3 students with processed hair. *Three*. I mused to myself. “That’s impressive!” In my high school days, the scenario was the opposite. Only three of us wore our natural hair in my grade 7 class — two of us were members of Christian churches

where chemically altered hair was prohibited⁶, and the other, with her looser 3B texture, was often praised for her ‘pretty hair’ and exempt from scrutiny. But now? There was a dramatic shift, one that I did not expect to see. Students were rocking their natural hair with great joy while moving through the ongoing weather of anti-Blackness (Sharpe, 2016).

I called this chapter “Hair Joy” because while I could hear the frustrating cries of the students calling for the grooming policy to change, I could also feel the joy radiating from many of the students as they shared their stories about their natural hair. This joy, I realized, was an act of reclaiming agency and subjectivity, a bold assertion of selfhood in an environment that seeks to suppress Black identity. Agency speaks to the power of marginalized groups to create spaces to resist and reshape oppressive systems, to take control of their identities and lives. In this case, the act of wearing natural hair in an environment that forces students to alter the texture of their hair becomes an act of resistance. With each coil, curl, and kink, Black girls are presenting counter-narratives and challenging the negative perceptions long tied to Afro-textured hair. Words like “beautiful,” “unique,” and “versatile” flow from their lips, each one infused with a sense of pride, joy, and deep reverence as they describe their natural hair. Imbuing Black hair with these positive words is a way of “speaking back” and reclaiming the cultural value Black hair held before Western colonization. This is a kind of anti-colonial resistance that Dei & Asgharzadeh (2001) speak about – a resistance that directly challenges the dominance of Western ways of being by reclaiming and celebrating Blackness.

Sitting under a tree with Destiny, I watched students with natural hair pass by. She nudged me, drawing my attention to the different hair types, and with a smile, she whispered, “I

⁶ There are some churches in Jamaica where changing one’s natural appearance - including, chemically altering one’s hair, piercing one’s ears, and tattooing one’s body - is considered immoral. They believe the body should remain the way God made it. This is my knowledge of growing up in churches with these teachings. Note, not all churches in Jamaica follow these principles.

just love to see Black girls rocking their natural hair.” It was clear that she felt a deep connection to the curls and textures that surrounded us. It made me think about the words I heard as a high school student wearing natural hair to school: “dry head,” “head tuff like wah,” “picky picky,” “peppa grain,” “haad fi comb” – words that signal that Black natural hair is nothing to be joyful about. These Jamaican Patois expressions are used to negatively label Afro-textured hair, much like the American terms “bad hair” and “nappy,” which have been used to describe hair that does not fit Eurocentric beauty ideals. They imply that the person’s hair is ugly, unmanageable, and difficult to style. In addition to those meanings, “picky picky” and “peppa grain” also denote that one’s hair is short and undesirable since long hair is often seen as a marker of beauty.

The relationship between Black identity and beauty ideals has evolved significantly over time, reflecting broader cultural and social changes. Ferrell (1993) asserts that through generations of socialization passed from parents to children, Black individuals were taught to view straight hair as desirable and beautiful, while Afro-textured hair was seen as undesirable and unattractive. Although these colonial views of Black hair linger, with hair shaming and biased school rules demanding students flatten or restrain their coils, there has been a noticeable shift in how students perceive their natural hair. What exactly sparked this change? What forces led these students to embrace their natural textures? What does it truly mean to love your hair when the world – and your school – constantly tells you to change your hair texture to fit the ideals of “proper grooming?” These questions filled me with wonder as I witnessed the joy on the students’ faces.

6.3 Embracing the Kinks

Of the six students who participated in the study, only one had ever chemically altered their hair. Abigail, who relaxed her hair starting in fourth grade, decided to return to her natural texture three years ago, following her conversion to Christianity. While not all churches in Jamaica require their members to wear natural hair, Abigail's church does. According to Innes Jr. (2021), hair is seen as a display of a person's inner spiritual state, and sometimes, hair rules are used to create a group identity in various religions. Langat (2022) further explains that for some Christian communities, natural hair symbolizes purity and a visible expression of one's dedication to God. Keeping one's hair natural is seen as a statement of alignment with God's design, as everyone is created in God's image, regardless of ethnicity, gender, or hair type (Langat, 2022, p. 84). Altering one's hair, in this view, is seen as a rejection of God's creation (Langat, 2022). In this context, "the big chop" – cutting off chemically straightened hair – becomes a symbolic act of reclaiming one's natural self, a spiritual transformation that signals acceptance as a child of God (Langat, 2022, p. 85).

Scholars like Stopler (2008) posit that Christianity, through its rules, maintains hegemonic patriarchal structures that justify women's subordination. Requiring women and girls to wear natural hair, in this regard, is seen as a form of patriarchal control. Nevertheless, Abigail credits her church for her positive view of natural hair. She explains that she loved her relaxed hair. It was easy to style, and she felt beautiful in it. She never wanted to have natural hair. Her attitude towards relaxed hair versus natural hair reflects Fanon's theorization of internalized inferiority, where straight hair is viewed as superior to natural hair. Adding to her negative perception of natural hair were the myriad of stories she had heard about the struggles of styling natural hair. These factors made her apprehensive about transitioning. "I had the notion that, oh,

natural hair is the worst thing on planet Earth,” she admitted, reflecting on the fear and misconceptions she had. “There I was thinking that the world would end if your hair is natural.” However, she decided to follow the teachings of her church and did a “big chop.” It took her a long while before she began to embrace her natural hair and come to realize just how versatile it could be. Now, with firm conviction, she declares, “I wouldn’t go back to processed hair.” This statement reflects not only a personal choice but also a psychological shift in perspective, as she finds happiness in both her spiritual growth and her natural self.

The other five participants have never chemically altered their hair. When asked if she had ever relaxed her hair, Brianna immediately responded, “No! I won’t do that. I thought about it, but I won’t.” Brianna explained that she had witnessed firsthand the damaging effects of chemical treatments on natural hair textures. “At one point, I was going to straighten my hair,” she recalls, “but a classmate tried it, and her hair never came back. I’m scared to do it now.” Brianna had experimented with straightening a small section of her hair using her cousin’s flat iron, but it took weeks for her curls to return to normal. Though the straightened hair appeared beautiful in the moment, the regret she felt when her curls failed to “*bounce back*” outweighed her desire for straight hair. “I won’t try it again,” she said resolutely.

Brianna’s story, much like that of many other students at Sankofa High, reflects a shift in perceptions about coily tresses and a reclamation of the narrative surrounding Black hair. Brianna’s refusal to lose her curls and coils challenges the dominant Eurocentric beauty norms that have historically held straight hair as the “matchless measure of beauty and value” (Mbilishaka & Hudlin, 2023, p. 717). This ontological shift can be read as a form of wake work — what Sharpe (2016) describes as “a mode of inhabiting and rupturing” the afterlives of slavery, where care, ancestral knowledge, and resistance converge in everyday acts of Black

living (p. 18). Here we see Black girls enact new ways of being and of surviving amidst the colonial climate. Although Brianna briefly considered straightening her hair and even tested a small section, this desire was not driven by self-hatred or the belief that straight hair was superior, as suggested by numerous studies. As Brianna explains, she simply wanted to experiment with a different style since Black hair is so versatile. She saw “straightened Black hair as just another hairstyle in the series of possibilities” (Tate, 2009, p. 43), not as the epitome of beauty. However, she refused to commit to waiting an extended period of time for her curls to return. Certainly, Brianna sees much beauty and value in Black natural hair.

Eva shared similar sentiments, explaining that she had witnessed the damage chemicals had caused to other people’s hair. Determined to avoid that harm, she has no interest in subjecting her own hair to such treatments. “It’s also too expensive for me,” she added, highlighting the ongoing costs of regular salon visits for chemical treatments. Black women participants in Mbilishaka’s (2018) research also expressed that hair straightening is quite costly, whether getting it professionally done or purchasing materials from beauty supply stores. Consequently, many Black women have embraced “DIY” - Do it yourself - approaches to styling their natural hair, opting for natural hairstyles that help prevent hair breakage (Mbilishaka and Hudlin, 2023). By keeping her hair natural, Eva feels she can sidestep both the financial and health-related burdens. “I don’t have to worry about that,” she said with a sigh of relief. Despite the challenges of managing her “thick” hair, Eva remains resolute in her decision not to chemically alter her hair. “Mi naah process mi hair” [I will never process my hair] she declared firmly, her words a proud affirmation of her commitment to embracing and loving her 4C textured coils.

Chantel, too, has never relaxed her hair and has no desire to do so. She avoids even a silk press or using heat to blow dry her hair, as she is committed to keeping her hair healthy by maintaining her natural kinks. However, she admits that keeping her hair healthy can be a challenge when she comes to school. To conform to the school's grooming rule, which states that hair must be "neatly restrained at all times," Chantel often does a slick-back hairstyle. This requires her to use a significant amount of hair wax to "smooth and flatten" her hair, applying it in sections to achieve a "neatly restrained" look as prescribed by the school. This styling product allows Chantel to keep her hair in place, but it contains ingredients like alcohol that can dry out the hair and scalp, so the excessive use of wax can be harmful to her natural hair, potentially leading to product buildup, breakage, and hair loss (Davis-Sivasothy, 2011). Outside of school, Chantel mainly wears protective styles like braids, cornrows, Chiney Bumps, and wigs to nurture the health of her 4C hair.

Historically, Black hair has been framed as "unmanageable," and many Black women have cited the difficulty of styling natural hair as the reason for chemically altering their hair (Barnett, 2016; Mbilishaka and Hudlin, 2023; Randle, 2015; Thompson, 2009). As Byrd and Tharp (2014) point out, "many Black people go through life never knowing the style and beauty options natural hair offers" (p. 156). However, for Chantel, the styles she rocks are an attestation to how natural hair is "manageable" and incredibly versatile. She recalls how, when she was younger, she hated her hair because her cousins would tug on it while styling it, causing her pain. Over time, Chantel found the right comb and hair oils that made her realize that her hair was manageable and fun to style. "I love my natural curls," Chantel said with genuine affection as she enthusiastically showed me photos of her hairdos, including the "wash and go" hairstyle she wore over the summer break when she did not have to restrain her curls with wax. "Wash and

go” is a low-maintenance style achieved by washing the hair, applying hair oil and/or leave-in conditioner, and letting the hair dry with minimal manipulation (Carol’s Daughter, 2023).

Chantel’s determination to maintain her Afro-textured curls and show off her curls/coily tresses exemplifies a cultural shift in how Black hair is understood.

Both Destiny and Fallon shared experiences of wanting to relax their hair during their younger years. Fallon recalled, “When I was younger, I wanted to have straight hair because my mom had cream hair, and it was so pretty and long, and I was like, I want my hair to stay down, because at that time, almost everyone had cream hair.” Destiny shared a similar story, recounting how she really wanted to relax her hair because most of the women in her family had already done so. “My mom, my aunts, everyone, basically,” she said. Her family members had processed their hair, citing the difficulty of managing their natural textures as their reason. Destiny vividly remembered going to the store and seeing relaxer kits marketed with images of kids with straight, silky hair. She profusely begged her mother to buy one, but her mother constantly refused. “It took me a while to accept my natural hair and learn to love it,” Destiny reflected on her journey to self-acceptance.

All the students in the study spoke with pride about embracing their natural kinks, curls, and coils. They all emphasize the importance of nurturing coily tresses to preserve their natural health. But this was not always the case in high schools in Jamaica. In years past, despite knowing the risks and long-term consequences of chemical relaxers, people still subjected their hair to harsh treatments. I, too, was no stranger to this contradiction. I vividly remember the searing burns from the chemicals, scarring my scalp in ways that left me cringing. Yet, I persisted. Why? As I explained in Chapters 2 and 5, straight, silky hair was the marker of professionalism and a “respectable lady” in Jamaican culture. Whiteness and its associated

features, including straight hair, have been used as the yardstick by which beauty and difference are measured (Johnson & Bankhead, 2014; Tate, 2007; Weekes, 1997). I felt the pain and saw the scars, but the burns were easily hidden beneath the sleek, flat, glossy tresses the relaxer produced. I had spent years being teased and shamed about my natural hair, so when I finally started to process my hair, I decided to tolerate the pain. The pain I endured was secondary to the perception that straightened hair conveyed success, discipline, beauty, femininity, and respectability. I did not hate my hair, but I wanted to be viewed in a positive light.

In discourse surrounding Black hair, the prevailing psychological interpretations often suggest that hair straightening is indicative of self-hatred, implying that Black folks are rejecting their natural hair in favour of Eurocentric ideals of beauty (Mbilishaka & Hudlin, 2023; Banks, 2000). However, these interpretations fail to account for the complex psychosocial factors that influence the choices made by Black folks regarding their hair. Scholars such as Althea Prince and Shirley Anne Tate argue that altering one's hair texture is not necessarily the result of internalized racism but rather a survival tactic rooted in respectability politics. Martin-Seaver (2024) describes respectability politics as a complex and ambivalent strategy that involves adjusting to the expectations of dominant cultural norms to achieve acceptance or success in professional and academic environments. Altering one's hair, with the use of chemical relaxers, texturizers, or any other method, becomes a practical accommodation technique to avoid shame, punishment, or any other negative treatment.

Today, the number of people relaxing their hair, whether due to internalized racism or respectability politics, is dwindling. Black women and girls are boldly embracing their natural hair and resisting colonial oppression. However, this generation of students is not the first to wear their hair natural. There has always been a movement toward natural hair.

6.4 Generations of Naturals

What I witnessed in Jamaica while carrying out this study was that the natural hair movement has gained significant traction. Black women and girls are boldly embracing their natural hair textures and resisting colonial beauty standards. While my initial surprise at the growing number of girls wearing natural hair to school might suggest that this is a new development, it is essential to recognize that this is not the first time Black people have embraced their natural hair. There has always been a movement toward natural hair, and its roots can be traced back long before the twenty-first century. The 1960s are credited with the rise of the modern Natural Hair Movement (Sherrow, 2023). This was the era of the Civil Rights and Black Power in the United States. Byrd and Tharps (2014) note that iconic figures like Angela Davis, Stokely Carmichael (who would become Kwame Ture in 1969), and the Black Panthers made the Afro a visual political statement in the United States, and it spread globally. Natural hair became a symbol of Black pride and anti-colonial resistance during the 1960s. These early expressions of natural hair were part of an ongoing resistance against the forced assimilation into European standards of beauty.

The embrace of natural hair did not come without setbacks. Throughout the 1980s and 1990s, the use of relaxers and perms became widespread, as many Black women conformed to European beauty standards in order to gain social mobility. The 2000s saw a resurgence of the natural-hair movement, largely fueled by social media platforms like YouTube and Instagram (Brown, 2018; Byrd & Tharp, 2014). Black women began sharing their hair journeys, offering tutorials on how to care for natural textures and creating communities of support. This digital space allowed people to find solidarity in their shared experiences and learn from each other's challenges and triumphs. Celebrities like Solange Knowles, Lupita Nyong'o, and Tracee Ellis

Ross also played a significant role in normalizing natural hair in the mainstream (Byrd & Tharp, 2014), encouraging a new generation to embrace their curls, locs, and Afros. Sales of chemical relaxers have dropped 34 percent since 2009, while sales of “natural” hair care products have increased exponentially (Norwood, 2018).

Jamaicans, too, have been pushing the boundaries. The Rastafari movement, for example, has long challenged colonial aesthetics and asserted natural hair as a spiritual and political expression of Black identity, liberation, and resistance against colonial oppression. In 2007, Zahra Redwood won the Ms. Jamaica Universe pageant competition and then represented Jamaica internationally in the Ms. Universe competition, proudly with her dreadlocks (see Figure 6.1). Several Jamaican pageant queens have proudly showcased their natural hair on the international stage, challenging the notion that beauty must adhere to Eurocentric beauty standards. Among them are Terri Karelle Reid, Miss Jamaica World 2005 (see Figure 6.2); Dr. Sanneta Myrie, Miss Jamaica World 2015 (see Figure 6.3); and Davina Bennett, Miss Jamaica Universe 2017 (see Figure 6.4). Their bold embrace of natural hair has garnered widespread attention and inspired many who once believed that beauty in pageantry could only conform to Western ideals.

Figure 6.1

Zahra Redwood, Miss Jamaica Universe 2007

Note. Zahra Redwood, crowned Miss Jamaica Universe 2007, the first Rastafarian to represent Jamaica in the international pageant.

Source. Jamaica, 2007

Figure 6.2

Terri Karelle Reid, Miss Jamaica World 2005

Note. Terri-Karelle Reid, Miss Jamaica World 2005, who represented Jamaica at the Miss World competition wearing her natural Afro.

Source. Johnson, 2023

Figure 6.3

Dr. Sanneta Myrie, Miss Jamaica World

2015

Note. Dr. Sanneta Myrie, Miss Jamaica World 2015, the first Miss World contestant to compete with dreadlocks.

Source. Campbell, 2020

Figure 6.4

Davina Bennett, Miss Jamaica 2017

Note. Davina Bennett, Miss Jamaica 2017, proudly wearing her natural Afro during the Miss Universe competition.

Source. Fasanella, 2017 - *Allure*

The natural hair movement has been growing, and with a new generation of Black girls, the movement is proven to be stronger than ever. The reasons are varied and complex, but undoubtedly, one of the major factors in the new era of the Natural Hair Movement is the increase in social media usage. YouTube, TikTok, Pinterest, and Instagram have become hubs for natural hair influencers and enthusiasts who share tutorials, tips, and techniques for maintaining and styling Afro-textured hair. These are counterspaces in which Black femininities are celebrated and nurtured (Curington, 2024). Virtual communities provide a wealth of haircare knowledge on everything from moisturizing routines to protective styling. Online platforms and natural hair influencers help Black girls nurture their coily tresses while fostering a sense of solidarity among online communities. Some of the students in the study noted that they engage with natural hair influencers to learn about hair care.

6.5 Conclusion

Today, an increasing number of Black girls are joyfully rocking their natural hair and pushing back at the institutional policies that seek to suppress Black hair. The narrative is shifting. As Fallon puts it, “It’s normal to have curly hair. Creaming [relaxing one’s hair] isn’t a rule, isn’t a law.” Black women and girls are fighting against the negative stereotypes attached to natural hair by using positive hair language to describe its curls, coils, and kinks. They are adopting a counter-discourse to remove the stigma of natural hair as unmanageable. They are practicing everyday hair resistance by proudly wearing their natural hair in settings that seek to suppress Black features. By choosing to embrace their natural hair, the students take control of their self-image and assert their ability to define beauty and identity on their own terms, rather than accepting the imposed norms of the colonizer. Anti-colonialism is about changing the narrative and reclaiming one’s history, knowledge, and way of being in spite of colonial imposition (Dei, 2008; Wane, 2006). The stories reveal how Black girls at Sankofa High School are exercising their agency to resist colonial norms and challenge negative perceptions of Black hair. The students are actively engaging in a decolonizing process, where they seek to free themselves from the mental shackles of colonial thinking that deem their natural coils as less desirable and not appropriate for school.

The students’ decision to wear their natural hair disrupts the afterlife of formal colonial rule and the racial capitalist machinery that profits from the denigration of Black hair. The global beauty industry, estimated at billions of dollars (Rosen et al., 2015), benefits from the false narrative that Afro-textured hair is a problem to be fixed. It turns anti-Blackness into a profit, selling “solutions” for hair deemed unruly, unprofessional, and inappropriate. Cedric Robinson (1983) reminds us that capitalism is inherently racial, with a foundation built on the production

of racial hierarchies that enable exploitation and accumulation. Audre Lorde (1984) likewise suggests that Black women's alienation from their own beauty is orchestrated and intentional, a mechanism of domination and exploitation that sustains the racial and gendered order. However, Black folks are not passively accepting colonial domination. The growing embrace of natural hair, with a decrease in relaxer sales by 26 percent between 2008 and 2013, and by 17 percent between 2006 and 2011 (Griffin & Lenzy, 2015, p. 26), reflects a widespread rejection of the notion that Black hair must be altered to be acceptable.

By choosing to joyfully wear natural hair, the students are grounded in a deep reckoning with systems of harm. Through their hair choices, we see another iteration of Sharpe's (2016) wake work as a practice of living and insisting on Black being in the hold of anti-Blackness. Wake work, in this respect, is also demonstrative of a rejection of the coloniality of femininity and a disruption of the economies that depend on commodification and psychological harm. In this 'wake', an increasing number of Black women and girls today are choosing to wear their hair in its natural state simply as a way of being. For many, the decision is less about making a political statement and more about self-acceptance (Johnson and Bankhead, 2014). By wearing their natural hair, they embody Marcus Garvey's call to "remove the kinks from the mind," through an inward shift that honours Black aesthetics. In this context, the students' embrace of their natural hair must be read as a rupture in the local climate of anti-Blackness that Jamaica's formal education seeks to uphold. Hair joy resists and persists.

Chapter 7

Let's Get Out of Hair

7.1 Contributions and Recommendations

This study intervenes in broader conversations on anti-Black racism and the coloniality of aesthetics in the Caribbean. It centers the lived experiences of Black girls by probing the question, *“How do female high school students experience school hair grooming policy?”* Through an anti-colonial lens, this research situates Black girls’ encounters with school authority within the enduring legacies of colonialism, where colonial ideologies continue to masquerade as neutral standards for all. I began this research manuscript by chronicling a series of news reports that catalyzed recent public discourse on hair discrimination in Jamaican schools. In response to these newsworthy incidents and public outcry, the Ministry of Education introduced a national hair grooming policy, but with a caveat. While the policy offers general guidelines, individual schools retained the power to enforce their own rules. What emerged then was not an abolition of discriminatory practices, but a loophole for schools to sustain colonial practices behind bureaucratic euphemisms.

To understand how these policies are lived and felt in a majority Black population, I turned to the narratives of girls attending Sankofa High School. This research found that the school complies with the Ministry’s directive of not naming any specific hairstyle in its written policy. On paper, the rule appears race-neutral, free from bias or hierarchies. But in practice, it renders natural Afro-textured hair a problem. The enforcement of the rule, particularly how administrators interpret “neatness,” reveals a racialized aesthetic order where Afro-textured hair is marked as undisciplined, uncivilized, and in need of control. Afros, puffs, and Bantu knots are read as deviating from the colonial norm of straight, flat, silky hair. Additionally, experiences of

hair shaming and demands by school authorities to change hairstyles show that texturism influences how the policy is enforced. Girls with looser curl patterns often encounter more leniency, while those with kinkier textures are subjected to closer surveillance and discipline.

Under the guise of preparing students for the future, girls are taught that success demands their hair be “tamed.” What the school fails to acknowledge is that it is using colonial logics to prepare students to maintain the norms of a colonial society. While administrators cling to colonial aesthetics disguised as “proper,” students are engaging with anti-colonial practices by imagining future possibilities (Evans-Winters & Love, 2015; Kelly, 2022). Drawing on the spirit of *Sankofa*⁷, looking back to the past with all its violences, for wisdom to guide the way forward (Thompson, 2025), students interrogate, oppose, and reject the logics of regulation imposed upon them. By joyfully wearing their natural hair, students enact an anti-colonial politics grounded in everyday resistance and a call for change. The change they seek is not inclusion within existing norms, but an undoing of the very foundations of the coloniality of aesthetics. The young girls summon the school to abandon the mental entanglements of racial-colonial-capitalism and instead centre healing, love, joy, and collective flourishing (Thompson, 2025).

Heeding the cry of the participants in this study and applying an anticolonial principle which stipulates that knowledge be mobilized to confront and undo colonial imposition (Simmons & Dei, 2012), I offer the following policy recommendations as a step toward building a more just and liberatory education system in Jamaica:

1. The Ministry of Education should abolish discretionary grooming policies. The so-called Student Dress & Grooming Policy released by the Ministry of Education offers a huge

⁷ While I use Sankofa High School as the pseudonym for the site of this research study, *Sankofa* in this sentence refers to the African concept originating from the Akan tradition of Ghana. *Sankofa* teaches that we must return to and reclaim our past in order to create a better future (Prendergast, 2011).

loophole for school administrators to exploit. The Ministry's admission that the policy is just a mere "guideline" (p. 2) for individual institutions to create and enforce their own policy is the state's strategic delegation of authority. Its refusal to take responsibility for the harms such policies produce is a cause for concern. Even though the Ministry of Education acknowledges that "slavery, plantation society and colonialism have left behind a preference for lighter skin colour and straighter hair textures, aligning them to opportunities for upward social mobility and economic opportunities" (p. 7), the policy does little to prevent both colourism and texturism in schools. It is imperative that the Ministry of Education enforce a standardized policy that holds schools accountable. A policy guide is just advisory. It is not legally binding.

2. There is a need for accountability structures. Although the Ministry of Education denounces the banning of Afrocentric hairstyles, this research reveals that schools do not necessarily follow this guideline. To ensure that schools end such discriminatory practices, mechanisms must be in place for students and families to report hair discrimination and for schools to be held accountable when they violate students' rights.
3. Radical transformation of Jamaica's education system is necessary. As Morrison and Milner (1995) note, Jamaica inherited an education system designed to serve the interests of white colonial rulers, and despite political independence, its structure remains largely untouched. It is time for Jamaica to create an education system to serve the masses. Students are longing to connect with their African heritage to pave the way for a 'post-colonial' future. An Afrocentric curriculum that demonstrates that Afro-Jamaican history does not begin on the slave ship is necessary. As Rodney (2019) points out, Black folks are "the only group of people in the world who deny [themselves], preferring to be

known as ‘negros’ rather than Africans” (p. 46). Black people distance themselves from Africa because they were taught to believe that Africans came from a barbarous society. Learning about African achievements before the arrival of the white man can help Black folks to build the confidence to reconnect with their African origins – confidence which slavery and colonialism have stolen from us (Rodney, 2019, p. 47). School curricula and teacher training that highlight the vibrant histories and cultures of African people prior to colonization can aid in removing the kinks from minds, not hair.

7.2 Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

I must acknowledge that this research unfolded within the contradictions of doing anti-colonial work inside a university structured by colonialism. While the project seeks to challenge dominant logics of power and knowledge production, academia requires that research to fit into its established patterns of thinking and presenting ideas, even if that research is trying to challenge or critique those very patterns. Awareness of this tension contributed to how the research was framed.

Furthermore, I tried to remain grounded in a purpose despite the structural and material constraints shaping this research. As a self-funded student, the financial burden of tuition, living expenses, and international travel significantly influenced the research design. While my original aim was to examine multiple schools across Jamaica, the high cost of travel and the need to limit time in the field meant the study focused on a single institution. These limitations are inseparable from the political economy of knowledge production itself, which privileges those with institutional funding and other study-related resources.

This qualitative research has demonstrated how institutional policies within a predominantly Black population can function as an instrument of oppression for Black girls.

Future research could expand on this work by engaging multiple school sites across different types of institutions, such as traditional high schools, technical schools, and comprehensive high schools, to examine how policy and practice varies across educational contexts. Future studies could focus on boys, who are also affected by hair grooming policies. I envision research that explores the gendered implications of these policies in greater depth. There is also room for engagement with parents and teachers by exploring their perspectives on the matter. Such efforts could push institutions to transform their policies toward greater justice and accountability.

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Appendix A

Information and Consent Sheet

Leading with Purpose.

INFORMATION SHEET AND CONSENT FORM

Title of Study: Natural Hairstyles in Schools
Ethics ID: Pro00139384

Contact Information

Principal Investigator: Meshia Brown, MEd student, Educational Policy Studies
Mailing Address: 11210 87 Ave NW, Edmonton, AB T6G 2G5
Email: meshia@ualberta.ca

Supervisor: Giselle Thompson, Assistant Professor, Educational Policy Studies
Mailing Address: 11210 87 Ave NW, Edmonton, AB T6G 2G5
Email: gthomps1@ualberta.ca

What is this about?

Your child is being invited to take part in a research study. Before you give consent, the primary investigator, Meshia Brown, is available to explain the project and you are free to ask any questions about anything you do not understand. You will be given a copy of this form for your records.

Why am I being asked to take part in this research study?

Your child has been asked to take part in the research because they attend a high school in Jamaica, which was invited and has agreed to participate in the Natural Hairstyles in Schools project. The participants in this study are female students who have experience wearing natural hairstyles to school.

What is the reason for doing the study?

The Natural Hairstyles in Schools project aims to understand the experiences of female students who wear natural hairstyles to school. The study focuses on girls who wear natural hairstyles. I would like to hear their experiences and learn about the factors that impact their choice of hairstyles and the impact the school hair rules have on the children's hairstyling practices.

What will the study involve?

If your child agrees to participate, they will be invited for an interview with Meshia Brown. The interview will be conducted on the school campus, allowing your child to share their experiences,

Faculty of Education

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thoughts, and feelings related to their hairstyling practices and the school's hair policies. The interview might take about 30 - 45 minutes. I want to make sure there is enough time to share thoughts and experiences. The interview will be audio-recorded for accuracy, and everything shared will be kept private. During the interviews, I will look at the hairstyle your child is wearing. This is to give me a visual understanding of the hairstyles that students wear to school. I will ask your child about the hairstyles they wear outside of school and how they differ. I will ask them to share stories about their hair and interactions with school administrators, teachers, and peers.

What are the risks and discomforts?

This is a low-risk study, and I hope that no one feels comfortable enough to talk about hairstyling practices and experiences. I understand that talking about personal experiences might be a little hard for some students. I will be careful and supportive during the talk. Your child can stop or take a break anytime. I want it to be a positive experience.

What are the benefits to me?

There may not be any direct benefit to you from participating in this research. However, some students find it helpful to share their thoughts and experiences about wearing natural hairstyles in school. This can contribute to a better understanding of this topic and help the school make better decisions about natural hairstyles and the students who wear natural hair.

Do I have to take part in the study?

No, your participation is entirely voluntary. You can decide not to take part, and it won't affect you or your child in any way. If you agree now but change your mind later, you can stop at any time before October 30, 2024. Individual interview transcripts will be sent to you via email, and you will have two weeks to review the contents and remove, change, or delete anything that you like.

To withdraw from the study, please contact Meshia Brown (meshia@ualberta.ca) or her supervisor, Giselle Thompson (gthomps1@ualberta.ca). I will be unable to withdraw data after October 30, 2024, because by that time, data analysis will be complete.

Will I be paid to be in the research?

There will be no payment for participating in this study.

Will my information be kept private?

I am committed to ensuring the confidentiality of all the information you provide. Your name will not be disclosed or published by the researchers. In interviews, an alternate name, chosen by you or assigned by the researcher, will be used to ensure anonymity.

During analysis, electronic data will be stored on a secure Google Drive at the University of Alberta. The information from this study will be seen only by members of the research group, i.e. the principal investigator and the supervisor. On occasion, this data will need to be checked for accuracy. For this reason, your data, including your name, may also be looked at by people from the Research Ethics Board.

I will make every effort within the confines of the law to maintain your privacy.

What will happen to the information or data that I provide?

The details you provide will be part of the research on natural hairstyles in schools, conducted by Meshia Bown. This information will be used to generate insights into the experiences of students with natural hairstyles in educational settings. The findings may be included in Meshia Brown's academic work, such as a thesis, and may be shared in presentations, publications, or educational materials. It's crucial to emphasize that your identity will be kept confidential throughout these uses.

After the research concludes, your data will be securely stored for a minimum of 5 years. Any physical records will be kept in locked cabinets, and electronic data will be stored on a secure University of Alberta Google Drive. The possibility of extending the storage beyond 5 years for future research will be considered. Your name will never be linked to electronic data, ensuring your privacy. If your data is ever linked with other information for research purposes, each new project will undergo an ethics review to ensure proper handling and confidentiality.

What if I have questions?

If you have any questions about the research now or later, please contact Meshia Brown (meshia@ualberta.ca) or her supervisor, Giselle Thompson (gthomps1@ualberta.ca).

If you have any questions regarding your rights as a research participant, you may contact the University of Alberta Research Ethics Office at reoffice@ualberta.ca or 780-492-2615. This office is independent of the study investigators.

How do I indicate my agreement to be in this study?

By signing below, you understand:

- That you have read the above information and have had anything that you do not understand explained to you to your satisfaction.
- That you will be taking part in a research study.
- That you may freely leave the research study at any time.
- That you do not waive your legal rights by being in the study.
- That the legal and professional obligations of the investigators and involved institutions are not changed by your taking part in this study.
- That you agree to the data being stored as part of a data repository

PARENT OR GUARDIAN CONSENT FORM

I..... give permission for my child(ren) to participate in the Natural Hairstyles in Schools.

- I confirm** that I am a legal decision-maker for the child(ren) listed below)
- I consent** to my child(ren) participating in this study
- I do not consent** to my child(ren) participating in this study

Signature: _____ Date: _____

Name (CAPS): _____

Child 1's name (CAPS): _____

Child 2's name (CAPS): _____

Appendix B

Interview Questions

Interview Questions

Biodata

Name:

Age:

Grade/Year Level:

Ethnicity:

Length of time attending the current school:

Questions

1. How do you typically style your hair for school?
2. What factors influence your choice of hairstyles? (religion, culture, time, etc.)
3. What do you know about the school hair grooming policy?
4. Are there hairstyles you would like to wear to school but are restricted by the rules? If so, which ones?
5. Have you ever worn a hairstyle to school that violated the rules? If yes, could you share that experience?
6. Do you have a clear understanding of which hairstyles are prohibited by the school's rules?
7. Can you share a specific experience you have had with the school's hair policy? How did it make you feel at the time?
8. How do school hair policies impact you personally?
9. Have you ever felt pressured to conform to the school's hair policy? If yes, can you describe that experience and how it made you feel?
10. Can you share instances where you witnessed or experienced resistance to the school's hair policy? How was it handled by the school administration?
11. In your opinion, what are the underlying reasons for enforcing certain hair policies in Jamaican schools?
12. What changes would you like to see in the school's hair policies, and why?
13. Any final thoughts you would like to share?